

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App;
4
5 use App\Mail\Mailers\UserMailer;
6 use App\Models\File;
7 use Illuminate\Notifications\Notifiable;
8 use Illuminate\Foundation\Auth\User as Authenticatable;
9 use Spatie\Permission\Traits\HasRoles;
10 use Tymon\JWTAuth\Contracts\JWTSubject;
11
12 class User extends Authenticatable implements JWTSubject
13 {
14     use Notifiable;
15     use HasRoles;
16
17     const USER_ACTIVE = '1';
18
19     /**
20      * The attributes that are mass assignable.
21      *
22      * @var array
23      */
24     protected $fillable = [
25         'name',
26         'email',
27         'password',
28         'is_admin',
29         'verification_token',
30         'status',
31     ];
32
33     /**
34      * The attributes that should be hidden for arrays.
35      *
36      * @var array
37      */
38     protected $hidden = [
39         'password',
40         'remember_token',
41         'verification_token',
42     ];
43
44     protected $dates = [
45         'created_at',
46         'updated_at',
47         'email_verified_at',
```

File - /project/app/User.php

```
48     ];
49
50     public function files()
51     {
52         return $this->hasMany(File::class);
53     }
54
55     public function sendPasswordResetNotification($token)
56     {
57         $mailer = new UserMailer();
58         $mailer->sendPasswordLinkTo($this, $token)->queue
59     };
60
61     /**
62      * Get the identifier that will be stored in the
63      * subject claim of the JWT.
64      *
65      * @return mixed
66      */
67     public function getJWTIdentifier()
68     {
69         return $this->getKey();
70     }
71
72     /**
73      * Return a key value array, containing any custom
74      * claims to be added to
75      * the JWT.
76      *
77      * @return array
78      */
79     public function getJWTCustomClaims()
80     {
81         return [];
82     }
83 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 if (!function_exists('cached_asset')) {
4     function cached_asset($path)
5     {
6         // Get the full path to the asset.
7         $realPath = public_path($path);
8
9         if (!file_exists($realPath)) {
10            return $path;
11        }
12
13        // Get the last updated timestamp of the file.
14        $timestamp = filemtime($realPath);
15
16        $path .= '?' . $timestamp;
17
18        return asset($path);
19    }
20 }
21
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http;
4
5 use App\Http\Middleware\JWTAuth;
6 use Illuminate\Foundation\Http\Kernel as HttpKernel;
7
8 class Kernel extends HttpKernel
9 {
10     /**
11      * The application's global HTTP middleware stack.
12      *
13      * These middleware are run during every request to
14      * your application.
15      *
16      * @var array
17      */
18     protected $middleware = [
19         \App\Http\Middleware\CheckForMaintenanceMode::
20         class,
21         \Illuminate\Foundation\Http\Middleware\
22         ValidatePostSize::class,
23         \App\Http\Middleware\TrimStrings::class,
24         \Illuminate\Foundation\Http\Middleware\
25         ConvertEmptyStringsToNull::class,
26         \App\Http\Middleware\TrustProxies::class,
27         \Spatie\Cors\Cors::class,
28     ];
29
30     /**
31      * The application's route middleware groups.
32      *
33      * @var array
34      */
35     protected $middlewareGroups = [
36         'web' => [
37             \Illuminate\Cookie\Middleware\
38             AddQueuedCookiesToResponse::class,
39             \Illuminate\Routing\Middleware\
40             SubstituteBindings::class,
41         ],
42
43         'api' => [
44             // 'throttle:60,1',
45             'bindings',
46         ],
47     ];
```

```
42
43     /**
44      * The application's route middleware.
45      *
46      * These middleware may be assigned to groups or used
    individually.
47      *
48      * @var array
49      */
50     protected $routeMiddleware = [
51         'jwtauth' => JWTAuth::class,
52         'permission' => \Spatie\Permission\Middlewares\
    PermissionMiddleware::class,
53         'auth.basic' => \Illuminate\Auth\Middleware\
    AuthenticateWithBasicAuth::class,
54         'bindings' => \Illuminate\Routing\Middleware\
    SubstituteBindings::class,
55         'cache.headers' => \Illuminate\Http\Middleware\
    SetCacheHeaders::class,
56         'signed' => \Illuminate\Routing\Middleware\
    ValidateSignature::class,
57         'throttle' => \Illuminate\Routing\Middleware\
    ThrottleRequests::class,
58         'verified' => \Illuminate\Auth\Middleware\
    EnsureEmailIsVerified::class,
59         'admin' => \App\Http\Middleware\IsAdmin::class,
60     ];
61 }
62
```

File - /project/app/Http/Requests/Api/User/UserPutRequest.php

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\User;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PutRequest;
6
7 class UserPutRequest extends PutRequest
8 {
9     protected function addRules(): array
10    {
11        return parent::addRules() + [];
12    }
13 }
14
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\User;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
6
7 class UserPostRequest extends PostRequest
8 {
9     protected function addRules(): array
10    {
11        return parent::addRules() + UserRequestBase::
  addRules();
12    }
13 }
14
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\User;
4
5 use App\User;
6 use Carbon\Carbon;
7
8 class UserRequestBase
9 {
10     public static function addRules()
11     {
12         return [
13             'data.attributes.name' => 'required|string|max
14 :50',
15             'data.attributes.email' => 'required|string|
16 email|max:255',
17             'data.attributes.password' => 'required|string
18 |min:6|confirmed',
19         ];
20     }
21 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\User;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
6
7 class UserUpdateProfileRequest extends PostRequest
8 {
9     protected function addRules(): array
10    {
11        return parent::addRules() + [
12            'data.attributes.name' => 'string|max:50',
13        ];
14    }
15 }
16
```

```
1 <?php
2
3
4 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\User;
5
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
7
8 class UserForgotPasswordRequest extends PostRequest
9 {
10     protected function addRules(): array
11     {
12         return parent::addRules() + ['data.attributes.
  email' => 'required|email'];
13     }
14 }
15
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\User;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
6
7 class UserChangePasswordPostRequest extends PostRequest
8 {
9     protected function addRules(): array
10    {
11        return parent::addRules() + [
12            'data.attributes.current_password' => '
  required',
13            'data.attributes.new_password' => '
  required_with:current_password',
14            'data.attributes.new_password_confirmation'
  => 'same:data.attributes.new_password',
15        ];
16    }
17 }
18
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\Project;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PutRequest;
6
7 class ProjectPutRequest extends PutRequest
8 {
9     protected function addRules(): array
10    {
11        return parent::addRules() + [];
12    }
13 }
14
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\Project;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
6
7 class ProjectPostRequest extends PostRequest
8 {
9     protected function addRules(): array
10    {
11        return parent::addRules() + ProjectRequestBase::
  addRules();
12    }
13 }
14
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\Project;
4
5 use App\Project;
6 use Carbon\Carbon;
7
8 class ProjectRequestBase
9 {
10     public static function addRules()
11     {
12         return [
13         ];
14     }
15 }
16
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\SamiConfig;
4
5 use App\Repositories\SamiConfigRepository;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PutRequest;
7 use Illuminate\Validation\Rule;
8
9 class SamiConfigPutRequest extends PutRequest
10 {
11     protected function addRules(): array
12     {
13         return parent::addRules() + [
14             'data.attributes.project_id' => [
15                 'sometimes',
16                 'integer',
17             ],
18             'data.attributes.type' => [
19                 'sometimes',
20                 'string',
21                 Rule::in(SamiConfigRepository::TYPES),
22             ],
23             'data.attributes.starting_date' => [
24                 'sometimes',
25                 'date_format:Y-m-d',
26             ],
27             'data.attributes.ending_date' => [
28                 'sometimes',
29                 'date_format:Y-m-d',
30             ],
31             'data.attributes.category' => [
32                 'sometimes',
33                 'string',
34                 Rule::in(SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORIES
35             ),
36             ],
37             'data.attributes.code' => [
38                 'sometimes',
39                 'string',
40             ],
41             'data.attributes.relative_range_start' => [
42                 'sometimes',
43                 'integer',
44             ],
45             'data.attributes.relative_range_end' => [
46                 'sometimes',
```

File - /project/app/Http/Requests/Api/SamiConfig/SamiConfigPutRequest.php

```
46     'integer',  
47     ],  
48 ];  
49 }  
50 }  
51
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\SamiConfig;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
6 use Illuminate\Validation\Rule;
7 use App\Repositories\SamiConfigRepository;
8
9 class SamiConfigPostRequest extends PostRequest
10 {
11     protected function addRules(): array
12     {
13         return parent::addRules() + [
14             'data.attributes.project_id' => [
15                 'required',
16                 'integer',
17             ],
18             'data.attributes.type' => [
19                 'required',
20                 'string',
21                 Rule::in(SamiConfigRepository::TYPES),
22             ],
23             'data.attributes.starting_date' => [
24                 'required',
25                 'date_format:Y-m-d',
26             ],
27             'data.attributes.ending_date' => [
28                 'required',
29                 'date_format:Y-m-d',
30             ],
31             'data.attributes.category' => [
32                 'required',
33                 'string',
34                 Rule::in(SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORIES
35             ),
36             ],
37             'data.attributes.code' => [
38                 'required',
39                 'string',
40             ],
41             'data.attributes.relative_range_start' => [
42                 'required',
43                 'integer',
44             ],
45             'data.attributes.relative_range_end' => [
46                 'required',
```

File - /project/app/Http/Requests/Api/SamiConfig/SamiConfigPostRequest.php

```
46     'integer',  
47     ],  
48 ];  
49 }  
50 }  
51
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnCategory;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PutRequest;
6
7 class ColumnCategoryPutRequest extends PutRequest
8 {
9     protected function addRules(): array
10    {
11        // @TODO: add/modify validations for your custom
  fields
12        return parent::addRules() + [];
13    }
14 }
15
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnCategory;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
6
7 class ColumnCategoryPostRequest extends PostRequest
8 {
9     protected function addRules(): array
10    {
11        // @TODO: add/modify validations for your custom
  fields
12        return parent::addRules() +
  ColumnCategoryRequestBase::addRules();
13    }
14 }
15
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnCategory;
4
5 use App\ColumnCategory;
6 use Carbon\Carbon;
7
8 class ColumnCategoryRequestBase
9 {
10     public static function addRules()
11     {
12         return [
13             'data.attributes.name' => 'required|string',
14         ];
15     }
16 }
17
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnDefinition;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PutRequest;
6 use Illuminate\Validation\Rule;
7
8 class ColumnDefinitionPutRequest extends PutRequest
9 {
10     protected function addRules(): array
11     {
12         return parent::addRules() +
  ColumnDefinitionRequestBase::addRules() + [
13             'data.attributes.column_number' => [
14                 'required',
15                 'integer',
16                 Rule::unique('column_definitions', '
  column_number')
17                     ->ignore($this->json('data.id'))
18                     ->where(function ($query) {
19                         return $query->where('file_id',
  $this->json('data.attributes.file_id'));
20                     })),
21             ],
22             'data.attributes.column_name' => [
23                 'required',
24                 'string',
25                 Rule::unique('column_definitions', '
  column_name')
26                     ->ignore($this->json('data.id'))
27                     ->where(function ($query) {
28                         return $query->where('file_id',
  $this->json('data.attributes.file_id'));
29                     })),
30             ]
31         ];
32     }
33 }
34
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnDefinition;
4
5 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
6 use Illuminate\Validation\Rule;
7
8 class ColumnDefinitionPostRequest extends PostRequest
9 {
10     protected function addRules(): array
11     {
12         return parent::addRules() +
  ColumnDefinitionRequestBase::addRules() + [
13             'data.attributes.column_number' => [
14                 'required',
15                 'integer',
16                 Rule::unique('column_definitions', '
  column_number')
17                     ->where(function ($query) {
18                         return $query->where('file_id',
  $this->json('data.attributes.file_id'));
19                     })),
20             ],
21             'data.attributes.column_name' => [
22                 'required',
23                 'string',
24                 Rule::unique('column_definitions', '
  column_name')
25                     ->where(function ($query) {
26                         return $query->where('file_id',
  $this->json('data.attributes.file_id'));
27                     })),
28             ]
29         ];
30     }
31 }
32
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnDefinition;
4
5 use App\Rules\ColumnCategoryExists;
6 use App\Rules\LeafColumnCategory;
7
8 class ColumnDefinitionRequestBase
9 {
10     public static function addRules()
11     {
12         return [
13             'data.attributes.category' => [
14                 'required',
15                 'string',
16                 new ColumnCategoryExists(),
17                 new LeafColumnCategory(),
18             ],
19             'data.attributes.project_id' => 'required|
integer|exists:projects,id',
20             'data.attributes.file_id' => 'required|integer
|exists:files,id',
21         ];
22     }
23 }
24
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\SamiConfigMilestone;
4
5 use App\Repositories\SamiConfigRepository;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PutRequest;
7 use Illuminate\Validation\Rule;
8
9 class SamiConfigMilestonePutRequest extends PutRequest
10 {
11     protected function addRules(): array
12     {
13         return parent::addRules() + [
14             'data.attributes.sami_config_id' => [
15                 'sometimes',
16                 'integer',
17             ],
18             'data.attributes.milestone_category' => [
19                 'sometimes',
20                 'string',
21                 Rule::in(SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORIES
22             ),
23             ],
24             'data.attributes.milestone_code' => [
25                 'sometimes',
26                 'string',
27             ],
28             'data.attributes.
29 milestone_relative_range_start' => [
30                 'sometimes',
31                 'integer',
32             ],
33             'data.attributes.milestone_relative_range_end'
34 => [
35                 'sometimes',
36                 'integer',
37             ],
38             ],
39         ];
40     }
41 }
42
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Requests\Api\SamiConfigMilestone;
4
5 use App\Repositories\SamiConfigRepository;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Requests\Api\
  PostRequest;
7 use Illuminate\Validation\Rule;
8
9 class SamiConfigMilestonePostRequest extends PostRequest
10 {
11     protected function addRules(): array
12     {
13         return parent::addRules() + [
14             'data.attributes.sami_config_id' => [
15                 'required',
16                 'integer',
17             ],
18             'data.attributes.milestone_category' => [
19                 'required',
20                 'string',
21                 Rule::in(SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORIES
22             ),
23             ],
24             'data.attributes.milestone_code' => [
25                 'required',
26                 'string',
27             ],
28             'data.attributes.
29 milestone_relative_range_start' => [
30                 'required',
31                 'integer',
32             ],
33             'data.attributes.milestone_relative_range_end'
34 => [
35                 'required',
36                 'integer',
37             ],
38             ],
39         ];
40     }
41 }
42
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Middleware;
4
5 use Closure;
6 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
7 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Auth;
8
9 class IsAdmin
10 {
11     /**
12      * Handle an incoming request.
13      *
14      * @param \Illuminate\Http\Request $request
15      * @param \Closure $next
16      * @return mixed
17      */
18     public function handle($request, Closure $next)
19     {
20         if (Auth::user() && (bool)Auth::user()->is_admin
21 ) {
22             return $next($request);
23         }
24         return abort(Response::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED);
25     }
26 }
27
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Middleware;
4
5 use Closure;
6 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
7 use Tymon\JWTAuth\Exceptions\JWTException;
8 use Tymon\JWTAuth\Exceptions\TokenExpiredException;
9 use Tymon\JWTAuth\Exceptions\TokenInvalidException;
10 use Tymon\JWTAuth\Facades\JWTAuth as JWTAuthFacade;
11 use Tymon\JWTAuth\Http\Middleware\BaseMiddleware;
12
13 class JWTAuth extends BaseMiddleware
14 {
15     /**
16      * Handle an incoming request.
17      *
18      * @param \Illuminate\Http\Request $request
19      * @param \Closure $next
20      * @return mixed
21      */
22     public function handle($request, Closure $next)
23     {
24         try {
25             JWTAuthFacade::parseToken()->authenticate();
26         } catch (TokenInvalidException $exception) {
27             return response()->json(['status' => 'Token is
invalid'], Response::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED);
28         } catch (TokenExpiredException $exception) {
29             return response()->json(['status' => 'Token is
expired'], Response::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED);
30         } catch (JWTException $exception) {
31             abort(Response::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED);
32         }
33         return $next($request);
34     }
35 }
36
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Middleware;
4
5 use Illuminate\Foundation\Http\Middleware\TrimStrings as
  Middleware;
6
7 class TrimStrings extends Middleware
8 {
9     /**
10      * The names of the attributes that should not be
  trimmed.
11      *
12      * @var array
13      */
14     protected $except = [
15         'password',
16         'password_confirmation',
17     ];
18 }
19
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Middleware;
4
5 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
6 use Fideloper\Proxy\TrustProxies as Middleware;
7
8 class TrustProxies extends Middleware
9 {
10     /**
11      * The trusted proxies for this application.
12      *
13      * @var array
14      */
15     protected $proxies;
16
17     /**
18      * The headers that should be used to detect proxies.
19      *
20      * @var int
21      */
22     protected $headers = Request::HEADER_X_FORWARDED_ALL;
23 }
24
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Middleware;
4
5 use Illuminate\Foundation\Http\Middleware\
  CheckForMaintenanceMode as Middleware;
6
7 class CheckForMaintenanceMode extends Middleware
8 {
9     /**
10      * The URIs that should be reachable while maintenance
11      * mode is enabled.
12      * @var array
13      */
14     protected $except = [
15         //
16     ];
17 }
18
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Controllers;
4
5 use Illuminate\Foundation\Bus\DispatchesJobs;
6 use Illuminate\Routing\Controller as BaseController;
7 use Illuminate\Foundation\Validation\ValidatesRequests;
8 use Illuminate\Foundation\Auth\Access\AuthorizesRequests;
9
10 class Controller extends BaseController
11 {
12     use AuthorizesRequests, DispatchesJobs,
13     ValidatesRequests;
14 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
4
5 use App\Http\Requests\Api\File\FilePostRequest;
6 use App\Jobs\ValidateFile;
7 use App\Repositories\ColumnDefinitionRepository;
8 use App\Repositories\FileRepository;
9 use App\Repositories\ProjectRepository;
10 use App\Transformers\Api\FileTransformer;
11 use App\Utils\Validation\State\RedisState;
12 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Controllers\
    BaseResourceController;
13 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
    BaseRepository;
14 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
    ResourceTransformerInterface;
15 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
16 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
17 use Pion\Laravel\ChunkUpload\Receiver\FileReceiver;
18 use Pion\Laravel\ChunkUpload\Exceptions\
    UploadMissingFileException;
19 use Pion\Laravel\ChunkUpload\Handler\HandlerFactory;
20
21 /**
22  * Class FileController
23  * @package App\Http\Controllers\Api
24  *
25  * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD)
26  */
27 class FileController extends BaseResourceController
28 {
29     /**
30      * @api           {get} /api/file/{id} Show
31      * @apiGroup      File
32      * @apiName       FileShow
33      * @apiDescription Show an entity.
34      * @apiParam      {integer} id Entity id.
35      * @apiSuccess    {object} data The entity.
36      * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
37      *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
38      *     {
39      *         "data":
40      *         {
41      *             "type": "file",
42      *             "id": "1",
43      *             "attributes": {
```

```
44     *         "user_id": "1",
45     *         "project_id": "1",
46     *         "file_name": "filename",
47     *         'size': 20000,
48     *         "preview": {
49     *             "headers": [
50     *                 "sample header 1",
51     *                 "sample header 2",
52     *                 "sample header 3"
53     *             ],
54     *             "data": [
55     *                 [
56     *                     1,
57     *                     2,
58     *                     3
59     *                 ],
60     *                 [
61     *                     "sample value 1",
62     *                     "sample value 2",
63     *                     "sample value 3"
64     *                 ],
65     *                 [
66     *                     "2018-01",
67     *                     "2018-02",
68     *                     "2018-03"
69     *                 ],
70     *             ]
71     *         }
72     *     }
73     * }
74     * }
75     */
76     protected function getTransformer():
ResourceTransformerInterface
77     {
78         return new FileTransformer();
79     }
80
81     protected function getRepository(): BaseRepository
82     {
83         return new FileRepository();
84     }
85
86     /**
87     * @api {post} /api/file/chunk/{project_id}/{type}
Chunk upload
88     * @apiGroup File
```

```
89     * @apiName FileChunk
90     * @apiDescription Uploads a file chunk, use form-
data.
91     * @apiParam {String} [file] File data.
92     * @apiParam {Number} [project_id] Project ID.
93     * @apiParam {String} [type] File type. Possible
values: data-demography, data-icd, data-atc,
94     *     data-icpm, bno, atc, oeno.
95     * @apiParam {Number} [chunk] Current chunk's number
it starts from 0.
96     * @apiParam {Number} [chunks] Total number of
chunks.
97     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
98     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
99     *     {
100    *         "done": 50
101    *     }
102    * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
103    *     HTTP/1.1 201 Created
104    *     {
105    *         "data":
106    *         {
107    *             "type": "file",
108    *             "id": "1",
109    *             "attributes": {
110    *                 "user_id": "1",
111    *                 "project_id": "1",
112    *                 "file_name": "filename",
113    *                 'size': 20000,
114    *                 "preview": {
115    *                     "headers": [
116    *                         "sample header 1",
117    *                         "sample header 2",
118    *                         "sample header 3"
119    *                     ],
120    *                     "data": [
121    *                         [
122    *                             1,
123    *                             2,
124    *                             3
125    *                         ],
126    *                         [
127    *                             "sample value 1",
128    *                             "sample value 2",
129    *                             "sample value 3"
130    *                         ],
131    *                     ]
```

```

132     *         "2018-01",
133     *         "2018-02",
134     *         "2018-03"
135     *     ],
136     *     ]
137     *     }
138     *     }
139     *     }
140     *     }
141     */
142     public function chunk($projectId, $fileType, Request
$request, ProjectRepository $projectRepository)
143     {
144         $project = $projectRepository->getByIdOrFail(
$projectId);
145         $receiver = new FileReceiver('file', $request,
HandlerFactory::classFromRequest($request));
146         if ($receiver->isUploaded() === false) {
147             throw new UploadMissingFileException();
148         }
149
150         $save = $receiver->receive();
151         if ($save->isFinished()) {
152             $fileRecord = $this->getRepository()->
saveFile(
153                 $save->getFile(),
154                 $fileType,
155                 $project->id
156             );
157             return $this->getItemResponse($fileRecord,
Response::HTTP_CREATED);
158         }
159         $handler = $save->handler();
160
161         return response()->json([
162             'done' => $handler->getPercentageDone()
163         ]);
164     }
165
166     /**
167     * @api {delete} /api/file/{id}
Delete
168     * @apiGroup File
169     * @apiName FileDelete
170     * @apiDescription Delete given File object &
remove file from storage.
171     * @apiParam {integer} id Entity id.

```

```

172     * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
173     *     HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
174     * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
175     *     HTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
176     */
177     public function destroy($id)
178     {
179         $this->getRepository()->deleteFileById($id);
180         return $this->getNoContentResponse();
181     }
182
183     /**
184     * @api {get} /api/file/validate/{id} Validate file.
185     * @apiGroup File
186     * @apiName Validate
187     * @apiDescription Triggers validator jobs for an
    uploaded file.
188     * @apiParam {Number} [id] File id.
189     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
190     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
191     *     {
192     *         "data":
193     *         {
194     *             "type": "file",
195     *             "id": "1",
196     *             "attributes": {
197     *                 "user_id": "1",
198     *                 "project_id": "1",
199     *                 "file_name": "filename",
200     *                 'size': 20000,
201     *                 "preview": {
202     *                     "headers": [
203     *                         "sample header 1",
204     *                         "sample header 2",
205     *                         "sample header 3"
206     *                     ],
207     *                     "data": [
208     *                         [
209     *                             1,
210     *                             2,
211     *                             3
212     *                         ],
213     *                         [
214     *                             "sample value 1",
215     *                             "sample value 2",
216     *                             "sample value 3"
217     *                         ],

```

File - /project/app/Http/Controllers/Api/FileController.php

```
218     *           [
219     *           "2018-01",
220     *           "2018-02",
221     *           "2018-03"
222     *           ],
223     *       ]
224     *   }
225     * }
226     * }
227     * }
228     */
229     public function runValidate($id,
ColumnDefinitionRepository $columnDefinitionRepository)
230     {
231         /** @var \App\Models\File $file */
232         $file = $this->getRepository()->getById($id);
233         $state = new RedisState($file->project_id, $file
->id, $file->user_id, $file->size);
234         ValidateFile::dispatch($file, $state,
$columnDefinitionRepository)->onQueue('default');
235         return $this->getItemResponse($file, Response:::
HTTP_OK);
236     }
237 }
238
```

```
1 <?php
2 /**
3  * Created by PhpStorm.
4  * User: mozsi
5  * Date: 2018.10.18.
6  * Time: 13:34
7  */
8
9 namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
10
11 use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
12
13 class TestController extends Controller
14 {
15     public function testendpoint()
16     {
17         return response()->json([
18             'data' => [
19                 'id' => 1,
20                 'type' => 'test',
21                 'attributes' => [
22                     'ping' => 'pong',
23                 ],
24             ],
25         ]);
26     }
27 }
28
```

```

1  <?php
2
3  namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
4
5  use App\Events\UserRegistered;
6  use App\Http\Requests\Api\User\
    UserChangePasswordPostRequest;
7  use App\Http\Requests\Api\User\UserForgotPasswordRequest;
8  use App\Http\Requests\Api\User\UserPostRequest;
9  use App\Http\Requests\Api\User\UserPutRequest;
10 use App\Http\Requests\Api\User\UserUpdateProfileRequest;
11 use App\Repositories\UserRepository;
12 use App\Transformers\Api\UserTransformer;
13 use App\User;
14 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Controllers\
    BaseResourceController;
15 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
    BaseRepository;
16 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\Fractal;
17 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
    ResourceTransformerInterface;
18 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
19 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
20 use Illuminate\Support\Carbon;
21 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Auth;
22 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Cookie;
23 use Illuminate\Support\Facades>Password;
24 use League\Fractal\Serializer\JsonApiSerializer;
25
26 /**
27  * Class UserController
28  * @package App\Http\Controllers\Api
29  *
30  * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD)
31  */
32 class UserController extends BaseResourceController
33 {
34     /**
35      * @api           {get} /api/user List
36      * @apiGroup      User
37      * @apiName       UserList
38      * @apiDescription List all User objects.
39      * @apiParam      {integer} page Page number
40      * @apiParam      {integer} limit Number of
    items per page
41      * @apiParam      {string} orderby The field
    name to order by

```

```

42     * @apiParam          {string} sortorder Ordering
    direction (asc|desc)
43     * @apiSuccess       {object} data List of User
    objects.
44     * @apiSuccess       {object} meta Pagination
    information.
45     * @apiSuccess       {object} links Pagination
    links.
46     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
47     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
48     *     {
49     *         "data": [
50     *             {
51     *                 "type": "user",
52     *                 "id": "1",
53     *                 "attributes": {
54     *                     'name': "username",
55     *                     'email': "user@example.com",
56     *                     'strain_identifrier': "sample id
string",
57     *                     'created_at': "2018-10-31 13:45:23",
58     *                     'updated_at': "2018-10-31 13:45:23",
59     *                     "roles": [
60     *                         "admin"
61     *                     ],
62     *                     "permissions": [
63     *                         "admin",
64     *                     ]
65     *                 }
66     *             },
67     *         "meta": {
68     *             "pagination": {
69     *                 "total": 1,
70     *                 "count": 1,
71     *                 "per_page": 50,
72     *                 "current_page": 1,
73     *                 "total_pages": 1
74     *             }
75     *         },
76     *         "links": {
77     *             "self": "http://localhost/api/user?limit=50
&page=1",
78     *             "first": "http://localhost/api/user?limit=
50&page=1",
79     *             "last": "http://localhost/api/user?limit=50
&page=1"
80     *         }

```

```

81     *     }
82     */
83     /**
84     * @api           {get} /api/user/{id} Show
85     * @apiGroup     User
86     * @apiName      UserShow
87     * @apiDescription Show a User object.
88     * @apiParam     {integer} id Entity id.
89     * @apiSuccess   {object} data The User object
90
91     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
92     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
93     *     {
94     *         "data":
95     *         {
96     *             "type": "user",
97     *             "id": "1",
98     *             "attributes": {
99     *                 'name': "username",
100    *                 'email': "user@example.com",
101    *                 'created_at': "2018-10-31 13:45:23",
102    *                 'updated_at': "2018-10-31 13:45:23",
103    *                 "roles": [
104    *                     "admin"
105    *                 ],
106    *                 "permissions": [
107    *                     "admin",
108    *                 ]
109    *             }
110     *         }
111     */
112     /**
113     * @api           {delete} /api/user/{id}
Delete
114     * @apiGroup     User
115     * @apiName      UserDelete
116     * @apiDescription Delete given User object.
117     * @apiParam     {integer} id Entity id.
118     * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
119     *     HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
120     * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
121     *     HTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
122     */
123     /**
124     * @api           {post} /api/user Store
125     * @apiGroup     User

```

```

126 * @apiName UserStore
127 * @apiDescription Store a new User object.
128 * @apiExample Example-Request:
129 * {
130 *     "data":
131 *     {
132 *         "type": "user",
133 *         "attributes": {
134 *             'name': "username",
135 *             'email': "user@example.com",
136 *             "roles": [
137 *                 "admin"
138 *             ]
139 *         }
140 *     }
141 * }
142 * @apiSuccess {object} data The created
user object.
143 * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
144 * HTTP/1.1 201 Created
145 * {
146 *     "data":
147 *     {
148 *         "type": "factory",
149 *         "id": "1",
150 *         "attributes": {
151 *             'name': "username",
152 *             'email': "user@example.com",
153 *             'created_at': "2018-10-31 13:45:23",
154 *             'updated_at': "2018-10-31 13:45:23",
155 *             "roles": [
156 *                 "admin"
157 *             ],
158 *             "permissions": [
159 *                 "admin",
160 *             ]
161 *         }
162 *     }
163 * }
164 */
165 /**
166 * @api {patch} /api/user/{id} Update
167 * @apiGroup User
168 * @apiName UserUpdate
169 * @apiDescription Update a User object.
170 * @apiParam {integer} id Entity id.
171 * @apiExample Example-Request:

```

```

172     *     {
173     *         "data":
174     *         {
175     *             "type": "user",
176     *             "id": "1",
177     *             "attributes": {
178     *                 'name': "username",
179     *                 "roles": [
180     *                     "admin"
181     *                 ]
182     *             }
183     *         }
184     *     }
185     * @apiSuccess           {object} data The User object
186     * @apiSuccessExample   {json} Success-Response:
187     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
188     *     {
189     *         "data":
190     *         {
191     *             "type": "user",
192     *             "id": "1",
193     *             "attributes": {
194     *                 'name': "username",
195     *                 'email': "user@example.com",
196     *                 'created_at': "2018-10-31 13:45:23",
197     *                 'updated_at': "2018-10-31 13:45:23",
198     *                 "roles": [
199     *                     "admin"
200     *                 ],
201     *                 "permissions": [
202     *                     "admin",
203     *                 ]
204     *             }
205     *         }
206     *     }
207     */
208     private $allowedFieldsToRegister = [
209         'name',
210         'email',
211         'password',
212     ];
213
214     /** @var \App\Repositories\UserRepository */
215     private $userRepository;
216
217     private $allowedFieldsToUpdate = [

```

```

218     'name',
219 ];
220
221 /**
222  * UserController constructor.
223  *
224  * @param $request
225  */
226 public function __construct(
227     Request $request,
228     UserRepository $userRepository
229 ) {
230     parent::__construct($request);
231     $this->userRepository = $userRepository;
232     //$this->middleware('role:user editor')->only(['
store', 'update', 'delete', 'show']);
233 }
234
235
236 /**
237  * @api {post} /api/user/register Register
238  * @apiGroup User Profile
239  * @apiParam {String} type Type of entity (user).
240  * @apiParam {String} name Name of the user.
241  * @apiParam {String} email Email address of the user
.
242  * @apiParam {String} password Password of the user.
243  * @apiParam {String} password_confirmation
Confirmation of the password.
244  * @apiParamExample {json} Example-Request:
245  * {
246  *     "data": {
247  *         "type": "user",
248  *         "attributes": {
249  *             "name": "asdasd",
250  *             "email": "asdahsd@asd.hu",
251  *             "password": "somepw",
252  *             "password_confirmation": "somepw",
253  *         }
254  *     }
255  * }
256  * @apiSuccess {object} data The stored user dataset.
257  * @apiSuccess {string} type Type of entity (user).
258  * @apiSuccess {number} id ID of entity.
259  * @apiSuccess {string} created_at When the user was
created.
260  * @apiSuccess {string} updated_at When the user was

```

```

260 updated.
261     * @apiSuccess {string} name Name of the user.
262     * @apiError {String} email Email address of the user
    .
263     * @apiErrorExample {json} Error-Response:
264     *     HTTP/1.1 422 Unprocessable Entity
265     *     {
266     *         "errors": [
267     *             {
268     *                 "status": "422",
269     *                 "source": {
270     *                     "pointer": "/data/attributes/data.
attributes.name"
271     *                 },
272     *                 "title": "Invalid parameter",
273     *                 "detail": "The data.attributes.name
field is required."
274     *             }
275     *         ]
276     *     }
277 */
278 /**
279  * Registers a new user.
280  *
281  * @param \App\Http\Requests\Api\User\UserPostRequest
$request
282  *
283  * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
284  */
285 public function register(UserPostRequest $request)
286 {
287     $requestData = $request->all();
288     $data = [];
289     foreach ($this->allowedFieldsToRegister as $field
) {
290         if (!isset($requestData['data']['attributes'
][[$field]])) {
291             continue;
292         }
293         $data[$field] = $requestData['data']['
attributes'][$field];
294     }
295
296     $this->validateAdditional($data, [
297         'email' => 'unique:users',
298         'name' => 'unique:users',
299     ]);

```

```

300
301     $data['verification_token'] = str_random();
302     $data['password'] = UserRepository::hash($data['
password']);
303
304     $userModel = $this->repository->store($data);
305     event(new UserRegistered($userModel));
306
307     return $this->getItemResponse($userModel,
Response::HTTP_CREATED);
308 }
309
310
311 /**
312  * @api {post} /api/user/change-password Change
password
313  * @apiGroup User Profile
314  * @apiName PostApiChangePasswordUser
315  * @apiDescription Change password of the user.
316  * @apiParamExample {json} Example-Request:
317  * {
318  *     "data": {
319  *         "type": "user",
320  *         "attributes": {
321  *             "current_password": "alma12345",
322  *             "new_password": "alma123456",
323  *             "new_password_confirmation": "
alma123456"
324  *         }
325  *     }
326  * }
327  * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
328  * HTTP/1.1 200 OK
329  * {
330  *     "data": {
331  *         "type": "user",
332  *         "id": "1",
333  *         "attributes": {
334  *             "created_at": "2018-04-09 16:17:06",
335  *             "updated_at": "2018-04-10 10:30:17",
336  *             "name": "admin",
337  *             "email": "adminuser@example.com"
338  *         }
339  *     }
340  * }
341  * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
342  * HTTP/1.1 403 Forbidden

```

```

343     * {
344     *     "errors": [
345     *         {
346     *             "status": "403",
347     *             "source": {
348     *                 "pointer": ""
349     *             },
350     *             "title": "Nincs hozzáférése a
funkcióhoz.",
351     *             "detail": ""
352     *         }
353     *     ]
354     * }
355     * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
356     *     HTTP/1.1 422 Unprocessable Entity
357     * {
358     *     "errors": [
359     *         {
360     *             "status": "422",
361     *             "source": {
362     *                 "pointer": ""
363     *             },
364     *             "title": "A jelenlegi jelszó nem
megfelelő",
365     *             "detail": ""
366     *         }
367     *     ]
368     * }
369     */
370     /**
371     * @param UserChangePasswordPostRequest $request
372     * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
373     */
374     public function changePassword(
UserChangePasswordPostRequest $request)
375     {
376         $requestData = $request->all();
377         $values = $requestData['data']['attributes'];
378         /** @var User $user */
379         $user = auth()->user();
380
381         if (!$user) {
382             abort(Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, 'Nincs
hozzáférése a funkcióhoz.');
```

```
385 $values)) {
386     abort(Response::HTTP_UNPROCESSABLE_ENTITY, 'A
    jelenlegi jelszó nem megfelelő');
387 }
388     $modifiedData['password'] = $values['new_password
'];
389
390     $modifiedUser = $this->repository->updateUser(
$user->id, $modifiedData);
391     return $this->getItemResponse($modifiedUser,
Response::HTTP_OK);
392 }
393
394 /**
395  * @api {patch} /api/user/update-profile Update
profile
396  * @apiGroup User Profile
397  * @apiName PatchApiUpdateProfile
398  * @apiDescription Update profile data of the user.
399  * @apiParamExample {json} Example-Request:
400  * {
401  *     "data": {
402  *         "type": "user",
403  *         "attributes": {
404  *             "name": "New username",
405  *         }
406  *     }
407  * }
408  * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
409  *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
410  * {
411  *     "data": {
412  *         "type": "user",
413  *         "id": "1",
414  *         "attributes": {
415  *             "created_at": "2018-04-09 16:17:06",
416  *             "updated_at": "2018-04-10 10:30:17",
417  *             "name": "New username",
418  *             "email": "adminuser@example.com"
419  *         }
420  *     }
421  * }
422  * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
423  *     HTTP/1.1 403 Forbidden
424  * {
425  *     "errors": [
426  *         {
```

```

427     *           "status": "403",
428     *           "source": {
429     *               "pointer": ""
430     *           },
431     *           "title": "Nincs hozzáférése a
funkcióhoz.",
432     *           "detail": ""
433     *       }
434     *   ]
435     * }
436     * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
437     *     HTTP/1.1 422 Unprocessable Entity
438     * {
439     *     "errors": [
440     *     {
441     *         "status": "422",
442     *         "source": {
443     *             "pointer": ""
444     *         },
445     *         "title": "Felhasználónév már létezik",
446     *         "detail": ""
447     *     }
448     *   ]
449     * }
450     */
451     /**
452     * @param UserUpdateProfileRequest $request
453     * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
454     */
455     public function updateProfile(
UserUpdateProfileRequest $request)
456     {
457         $requestData = $request->all();
458         $values = [];
459         foreach ($this->allowedFieldsToUpdate as $field
) {
460             if (!isset($requestData['data']['attributes'
][[$field]])) {
461                 continue;
462             }
463             $values[$field] = $requestData['data']['
attributes'][[$field]];
464         }
465         /** @var User $user */
466         $user = auth()->user();
467
468         if (!$user) {

```

```
469         abort(Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, 'Nincs
hozzáférése a funkcióhoz.');
```

```
470     }
471
472     $modifiedUser = $this->repository->updateUser(
$user->id, $values);
473     return $this->getItemResponse($modifiedUser,
Response::HTTP_OK);
474 }
475 /**
476  * @api {delete} /api/user/remove Delete user
477  * @apiGroup User Profile
478  * @apiName ApiAuthRemoveUser
479  * @apiDescription Delete logged in user with all
related content.
480  * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
481  *   HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
482  * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
483  *   HTTP/1.1 403 Forbidden
484  * {
485  *   "errors": [
486  *     {
487  *       "status": "403",
488  *       "source": {
489  *         "pointer": ""
490  *       },
491  *       "title": "Nincs hozzáférése a
funkcióhoz.",
492  *       "detail": ""
493  *     }
494  *   ]
495  * }
496  */
497 public function remove()
498 {
499     $user = auth()->user();
500     if (!$user) {
501         abort(Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, 'Nincs
hozzáférése a funkcióhoz.');
```

```
502     }
503     $this->repository->delete($user->id);
504     return $this->getNoContentResponse();
505 }
506
507 /**
508  * @api {post} /api/user/forgotpassword Forgot
password
```

```

509     * @apiGroup User Profile
510     * @apiName UserForgotPassword
511     * @apiDescription Triggers password reminder email.
512     * @apiParamExample {json} Example-Request:
513     * {
514     *     "data": {
515     *         "type": "user",
516     *         "attributes": {
517     *             "email": "user@example.com",
518     *         }
519     *     }
520     * }
521     * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
522     *     HTTP/1.1 204 No content
523     */
524     public function forgotPassword(
525         UserForgotPasswordRequest $request)
526     {
527         $input = $request->input();
528         Password::broker()->sendResetLink(['email' =>
529             $input['data']['attributes']['email']]);
530         return $this->getNoContentResponse();
531     }
532     /**
533     * Get a JWT token via given credentials.
534     *
535     * @param \Illuminate\Http\Request $request
536     *
537     * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
538     */
539     public function login(Request $request)
540     {
541         $credentialsData = $request->only('data.
542             attributes.email', 'data.attributes.password');
543         $credentials = $credentialsData['data']['
544             attributes'];
545         $user = $this->userRepository->getUserByEmail(
546             $credentials['email']);
547         $token = $this->getLoginToken($credentials, $user
548         );
549         if (!$token) {
550             return $this->jsonResponseUser(
551                 'Helytelen email cím vagy jelszó',
552                 Response::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED
553             );
554         }
555     }

```

```
550     }
551
552     $tokenLifeTime = $this->guard()->factory()->
getTTL();
553     return $this
554         ->respondWithToken($token)
555         ->cookie('token', $token, $tokenLifeTime, '/',
$request->getBaseUrl(), $request->isSecure(), false);
556     }
557
558     /**
559      * Log the user out (Invalidate the token)
560      *
561      * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
562      */
563     public function logout()
564     {
565         $this->guard()->logout();
566         return response()
567             ->json(['message' => 'Successfully logged out'
])
568             ->withCookie(Cookie::forget('token'));
569     }
570
571     /**
572      * Refresh a token.
573      *
574      * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
575      */
576     public function refresh(Request $request)
577     {
578         $token = auth()->refresh();
579         $tokenLifeTime = $this->guard()->factory()->
getTTL();
580         return $this
581             ->respondWithToken($token)
582             ->cookie('token', $token, $tokenLifeTime, '/',
, $request->getBaseUrl(), $request->isSecure(), false);
583     }
584
585     /**
586      * Get the authenticated User
587      *
588      * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
589      */
590     public function mydata()
591     {
```

```
592     $fractal = new Fractal(new JsonApiSerializer());
593     return response()->json(
594         $fractal->item(
595             $this->guard()->user(),
596             new UserTransformer(),
597             'user'
598         )
599     );
600 }
601
602 public function store(UserPostRequest $request)
603 {
604     $data = $request->input('data');
605     $model = $this->getRepository()->createUser($data
606 ['attributes']);
607     return $this->getItemResponse($model, Response::
608 HTTP_CREATED);
609 }
610
611 public function update($id, UserPutRequest $request)
612 {
613     $input = $request->input();
614     $values = $input['data']['attributes'];
615
616     $user = auth()->user();
617     if (!$user) {
618         return $this->jsonResponseUser(
619             'Nincs hozzáférése a funkcióhoz.',
620             Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN
621         );
622     }
623     $modifiedUser = $this->repository->updateUser($id
624 , $values);
625     return $this->getItemResponse($modifiedUser,
626 Response::HTTP_OK);
627 }
628
629 /**
630  * Return token if datass is valid
631  * @param $credentials
632  * @param $user
633  *
634  * @return mixed
635  */
636 private function getLoginToken($credentials, $user)
```

```
635         if ($user && !(bool)$user->status) {
636             return false;
637         }
638
639         $token = $this
640             ->guard()
641             ->attempt($credentials);
642
643         if (!$token && md5($credentials['password']) ===
644             $user['old_password']) {
645             $this->userRepository->updateUser(
646                 $user['id'],
647                 ['old_password' => '', 'password' =>
648                 $credentials['password']]
649             );
650             $token = $this
651                 ->guard()
652                 ->attempt($credentials);
653         }
654         return $token;
655     }
656
657     private function jsonResponseUser($detail,
658         $responseCode)
659     {
660         return response()->json(['errors' => [
661             [
662                 'status' => $responseCode,
663                 'detail' => $detail,
664             ]
665         ]], $responseCode);
666     }
667
668     /**
669     * Get the token array structure.
670     *
671     * @param string $token
672     *
673     * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
674     */
675     protected function respondWithToken($token)
676     {
677         return response()->json([
678             'access_token' => $token,
679             'token_type' => 'bearer',
680             'expires_in' => $this->guard()->factory()->
681             getTTL(),
```

```
678     });
679 }
680
681 protected function validatePasswordFields(User $user
, $values)
682 {
683     $userCredentials = [
684         'email' => $user->email,
685         'password' => $values['current_password'] ??
'',
686     ];
687
688     return auth()->validate($userCredentials);
689 }
690
691 protected function getTransformer():
ResourceTransformerInterface
692 {
693     return new UserTransformer();
694 }
695
696 protected function getRepository(): BaseRepository
697 {
698     return new UserRepository();
699 }
700
701 /**
702  * Get the guard to be used during authentication.
703  *
704  * @return \Illuminate\Contracts\Auth\Guard
705  */
706 public function guard()
707 {
708     return Auth::guard();
709 }
710
711 protected function getFilterInfo(Request $request)
712 {
713     return [
714         'name' => $request->get('name'),
715         'email' => $request->get('email'),
716     ];
717 }
718 }
719
```

```

1  <?php
2
3  namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
4
5  use App\Events\ProjectDeleted;
6  use App\Events\ProjectUpdated;
7  use App\Http\Requests\Api\Project\ProjectPostRequest;
8  use App\Http\Requests\Api\Project\ProjectPutRequest;
9  use App\Jobs\CallMagicMethod;
10 use App\Repositories\FileRepository;
11 use App\Repositories\ProjectRepository;
12 use App\Repositories\SamiConfigRepository;
13 use App Transformers\Api\ProjectTransformer;
14 use App Transformers\Api\SamiConfigTransformer;
15 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Controllers\
    BaseResourceController;
16 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
    BaseRepository;
17 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
    ResourceTransformerInterface;
18 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
19 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
20
21 class ProjectController extends BaseResourceController
22 {
23     /**
24      * @api           {get} /api/project List
25      * @apiGroup     Project
26      * @apiName      ProjectList
27      * @apiDescription List all entity.
28      * @apiParam     {integer} page Page number
29      * @apiParam     {integer} limit Number of
    items per page
30      * @apiParam     {string} orderby The field
    name to order by
31      * @apiParam     {string} sortorder Ordering
    direction (asc|desc)
32      * @apiSuccess   {object} data The entity.
33      * @apiSuccess   {object} meta Pagination
    information.
34      * @apiSuccess   {object} links Pagination
    links.
35      * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
36      *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
37      *     {
38      *         "data": [
39      *             {

```

```

40     *         "type": "project",
41     *         "id": "1",
42     *         "attributes": {
43     *             "name": "sample string",
44     *             "archived": 1,
45     *             "upload_done": 1,
46     *             "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
47     *             "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
48     *         }
49     *     }
50     * ],
51     *     "meta": {
52     *         "pagination": {
53     *             "total": 1,
54     *             "count": 1,
55     *             "per_page": 50,
56     *             "current_page": 1,
57     *             "total_pages": 1
58     *         }
59     *     },
60     *     "links": {
61     *         "self": "http://localhost/api/project?limit
=50&page=1",
62     *         "first": "http://localhost/api/project?
limit=50&page=1",
63     *         "last": "http://localhost/api/project?limit
=50&page=1"
64     *     }
65     * }
66 */
67 /**
68  * @api           {get} /api/project/{id} Show
69  * @apiGroup     Project
70  * @apiName      ProjectShow
71  * @apiDescription Show an entity.
72  * @apiParam     {integer} id Entity id.
73  * @apiSuccess   {object} data The entity.
74  * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
75  *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
76  *     {
77  *         "data":
78  *         {
79  *             "type": "project",
80  *             "id": "1",
81  *             "attributes": {
82  *                 "name": "sample string",
83  *                 "archived": 1,

```

```

84     *           "upload_done": 1,
85     *           "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
86     *           "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
87     *         }
88     *     }
89     * }
90 */
91 /**
92     * @api           {delete} /api/project/{id}
Delete
93     * @apiGroup       Project
94     * @apiName         ProjectDelete
95     * @apiDescription Delete the given entity.
96     * @apiParam       {integer} id Entity id.
97     * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
98     *     HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
99     * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
100    *     HTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
101 */
102 protected function getTransformer():
ResourceTransformerInterface
103     {
104         return new ProjectTransformer();
105     }
106
107 protected function getRepository(): BaseRepository
108     {
109         return new ProjectRepository();
110     }
111
112 /**
113     * @api           {post} /api/project Store
114     * @apiGroup       Project
115     * @apiName         ProjectStore
116     * @apiDescription Store a new entity.
117     * @apiExample     Example-Request:
118     *     {
119     *         "data":
120     *         {
121     *             "type": "project",
122     *             "attributes": {
123     *                 "name": "sample string",
124     *                 "archived": 1,
125     *                 "upload_done": 1,
126     *             }
127     *         }
128     *     }

```

```

129     * @apiSuccess           {object} data The created
entity.
130     * @apiSuccessExample   {json} Success-Response:
131     *     HTTP/1.1 201 Created
132     *     {
133     *         "data":
134     *         {
135     *             "type": "project",
136     *             "id": "1",
137     *             "attributes": {
138     *                 "name": "sample string",
139     *                 "archived": 1,
140     *                 "upload_done": 1,
141     *                 "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
142     *                 "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
143     *             }
144     *         }
145     *     }
146     */
147     public function store(ProjectPostRequest $request)
148     {
149         $data = $request->input('data');
150         $model = $this->getRepository()->store($data['
attributes']);
151         return $this->getItemResponse($model, Response::
HTTP_CREATED);
152     }
153
154     /**
155     * @api                   {patch} /api/project/{id}
Update
156     * @apiGroup             Project
157     * @apiName               ProjectUpdate
158     * @apiDescription       Update an entity.
159     * @apiParam             {integer} id Entity id.
160     * @apiExample           Example-Request:
161     *     {
162     *         "data":
163     *         {
164     *             "type": "project",
165     *             "id": "1",
166     *             "attributes": {
167     *                 "name": "sample string",
168     *                 "archived": 1,
169     *                 "upload_done": 1,
170     *             }
171     *         }

```

```

172     *     }
173     * @apiSuccess           {object} data The entity.
174     * @apiSuccessExample  {json} Success-Response:
175     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
176     *     {
177     *         "data":
178     *         {
179     *             "type": "project",
180     *             "id": "1",
181     *             "attributes": {
182     *                 "name": "sample string",
183     *                 "archived": 1,
184     *                 "upload_done": 1,
185     *                 "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
186     *                 "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
187     *             }
188     *         }
189     *     }
190     */
191     public function update($id, ProjectPutRequest
192     $request)
193     {
194         $data = $request->input('data');
195         $model = $this->getRepository()->update($id,
196         $data['attributes']);
197         event(new ProjectUpdated($model));
198     }
199     protected function getFilterInfo(Request $request)
200     {
201         $filters = [
202             'name' => $request->get('name'),
203         ];
204         if ($request->exists('archived')) {
205             $filters['archived'] = $request->get('
206     archived') ? 1 : -1;
207         }
208         if ($request->exists('upload_done')) {
209             $filters['upload_done'] = $request->get('
210     upload_done') ? 1 : -1;
211         }
212         return $filters;
213     }
214     /**
215     * @api           {delete} /api/project/{id}

```

```

214 Delete
215     * @apiGroup      Project
216     * @apiName      ProjectDelete
217     * @apiDescription Delete given Project object
    & remove all project files from storage.
218     * @apiParam      {integer} id Entity id.
219     * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
220     *     HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
221     * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
222     *     HTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
223     */
224     public function destroy($id)
225     {
226         $project = $this->getRepository()->getById($id);
227         event(new ProjectDeleted($project));
228
229         return parent::destroy($id);
230     }
231
232     /**
233     * @api           {patch} /api/project/run_sami
    /{id} Run Sami
234     * @apiGroup      Project
235     * @apiName      ProjectRunSami
236     * @apiDescription Run Sami function.
237     * @apiParam      {integer} id Entity id.
238     * @apiSuccess    {object} data The entity.
239     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
240     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
241     *     {
242     *         "data":
243     *         {
244     *             "type": "project",
245     *             "id": "1",
246     *             "attributes": {
247     *                 "name": "sample string",
248     *                 "archived": 1,
249     *                 "upload_done": 1,
250     *                 "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
251     *                 "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
252     *             }
253     *         }
254     *     }
255     */
256     public function runSami($id)
257     {
258         $model = $this->getRepository()->update($id, ['

```

```

258     'upload_done' => true,]);
259     return $this->getItemResponse($model);
260 }
261
262 /**
263  * @api {patch} /api/project/
call_magic_method/{id} Run calculation
264  * @apiGroup Project
265  * @apiName ProjectCallMagicMethod
266  * @apiDescription Run calculation.
267  * @apiParam {integer} id Entity id.
268  * @apiSuccess {object} data The entity.
269  * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
270  *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
271  *     {
272  *         "data":
273  *         {
274  *             "type": "project",
275  *             "id": "1",
276  *             "attributes": {
277  *                 "name": "sample string",
278  *                 "archived": 1,
279  *                 "upload_done": 1,
280  *                 "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
281  *                 "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
282  *             }
283  *         }
284  *     }
285  */
286     public function callMagicMethod($id)
287     {
288         $projectId = $id;
289
290         $samiConfigItem = (new SamiConfigRepository())->
getByIdOrFail($projectId);
291         $samiConfigTransformer = new
SamiConfigTransformer();
292         $samiConfig = $this->fractal->item(
293             $samiConfigItem,
294             $samiConfigTransformer,
295             $samiConfigTransformer::getResourceKey()
296         );
297
298         CallMagicMethod::dispatch($projectId, $samiConfig
)->onQueue('magic');
299
300         $resource = $this->repository->getByIdOrFail(

```

File - /project/app/Http/Controllers/Api/ProjectController.php

```
300 $projectId);  
301     return $this->getItemResponse($resource);  
302 }  
303 }  
304
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
4
5 use App\Http\Requests\Api\SamiConfig\SamiConfigPostRequest
;
6 use App\Http\Requests\Api\SamiConfig\SamiConfigPutRequest;
7 use App\Repositories\SamiConfigRepository;
8 use App Transformers\Api\SamiConfigTransformer;
9 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Controllers\
BaseResourceController;
10 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
BaseRepository;
11 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator Transformers\
ResourceTransformerInterface;
12 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
13 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
14
15 class SamiConfigController extends BaseResourceController
16 {
17     /**
18      * @api           {get} /api/sami_config List
19      * @apiGroup      SamiConfig
20      * @apiName       SamiConfigList
21      * @apiDescription List all entity.
22      * @apiParam      {integer} page Page number
23      * @apiParam      {integer} limit Number of
items per page
24      * @apiParam      {string} orderby The field
name to order by
25      * @apiParam      {string} sortorder Ordering
direction (asc|desc)
26      * @apiSuccess    {object} data The entity.
27      * @apiSuccess    {object} meta Pagination
information.
28      * @apiSuccess    {object} links Pagination
links.
29      * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
30      *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
31      *     {
32      *         "data": [
33      *             {
34      *                 "type": "sami_config",
35      *                 "id": "1",
36      *                 "attributes": {
37      *                     "project_id": 1,
38      *                     "factors": {
```

```

39     *         "sample key": "sample value"
40     *     },
41     *     "type": "segmentation",
42     *     "name": "Name",
43     *     "starting_date": "2012-01-01",
44     *     "ending_date": "2017-01-01",
45     *     "category": "BNO",
46     *     "code": "i1000",
47     *     "relative_range_start": 24,
48     *     "relative_range_end": 12,
49     *     "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
50     *     "updated_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
51     *     "milestones": {
52     *         "data": [
53     *             {
54     *                 "type": "
sami_config_milestone",
55     *                 "id": "1",
56     *                 "attributes": {
57     *                     "sami_config_id": 1,
58     *                     "milestone_category
": "BNO",
59     *                     "milestone_code": "
i1000",
60     *                     "
milestone_relative_range_start": 24,
61     *                     "
milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
62     *                     "milestone_frequency
": 5,
63     *                     "created_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:12",
64     *                     "updated_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:12"
65     *                 }
66     *             },
67     *             {
68     *                 "type": "
sami_config_milestone",
69     *                 "id": "2",
70     *                 "attributes": {
71     *                     "sami_config_id": 1,
72     *                     "milestone_category
": "BNO",
73     *                     "milestone_code": "
i1000",
74     *                     "

```

```
74 milestone_relative_range_start": 24,  
75     *  
milestone_relative_range_end": 12,  
76     * "milestone_frequency  
": 5,  
77     * "created_at": "2019-  
07-25 07:19:16",  
78     * "updated_at": "2019-  
07-25 07:19:16"  
79     * }  
80     * }  
81     * ]  
82     * },  
83     * "chartResult": {  
84     *     "clusterCharts": [  
85     *     {  
86     *         "title": "Cluster size 1  
",  
87     *         "data": [  
88     *         {  
89     *             "x": 1,  
90     *             "y": 10  
91     *         },  
92     *         {  
93     *             "x": 2,  
94     *             "y": 13  
95     *         }  
96     *     ]  
97     *     }  
98     * ],  
99     * "boxPlot": {  
100    *     "title": "Box Plot",  
101    *     "data": [  
102    *     {  
103    *         "x": 1,  
104    *         "min": 2,  
105    *         "median": 5,  
106    *         "max": 10,  
107    *         "q1": 3,  
108    *         "q3": 7  
109    *     },  
110    *     ]  
111    *     }  
112    * },  
113    * "gridResult": [  
114    *     {  
115    *         "ssn": "312-876-924",
```

```

116     *         "bno": "D1810",
117     *         "atc": "A02BC01",
118     *         "oeno": "3501B",
119     *         "mi1": "2001.12.-2005.01.",
120     *         "mi2": "2001.12.-2005.01.",
121     *         "mi3": "2001.12.-2005.01.",
122     *         "death": "yes"
123     *     }
124     * ]
125     * }
126     * }
127     * ],
128     * "meta": {
129     *     "pagination": {
130     *         "total": 1,
131     *         "count": 1,
132     *         "per_page": 50,
133     *         "current_page": 1,
134     *         "total_pages": 1
135     *     }
136     * },
137     * "links": {
138     *     "self": "http://localhost/api/sami_config?
limit=50&page=1",
139     *     "first": "http://localhost/api/sami_config
?limit=50&page=1",
140     *     "last": "http://localhost/api/sami_config?
limit=50&page=1"
141     *     }
142     * }
143     */
144     /**
145     * @api          {get} /api/sami_config/{id}
Show
146     * @apiGroup    SamiConfig
147     * @apiName      SamiConfigShow
148     * @apiDescription Show an entity.
149     * @apiParam    {integer} id Entity id.
150     * @apiSuccess  {object} data The entity.
151     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
152     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
153     *     {
154     *         "data":
155     *         {
156     *             "type": "sami_config",
157     *             "id": "1",
158     *             "attributes": {

```

```
159     *           "project_id": 1,
160     *           "factors": {
161     *             "sample key": "sample value"
162     *           },
163     *           "type": "segmentation",
164     *           "name": "Name",
165     *           "starting_date": "2012-01-01",
166     *           "ending_date": "2017-01-01",
167     *           "category": "BNO",
168     *           "code": "i1000",
169     *           "relative_range_start": 24,
170     *           "relative_range_end": 12,
171     *           "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
172     *           "updated_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
173     *           "milestones": {
174     *             "data": [
175     *               {
176     *                 "type": "
sami_config_milestone",
177     *                 "id": "1",
178     *                 "attributes": {
179     *                   "sami_config_id": 1,
180     *                   "milestone_category
": "BNO",
181     *                   "milestone_code": "
i1000",
182     *                   "
milestone_relative_range_start": 24,
183     *                   "
milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
184     *                   "milestone_frequency
": 5,
185     *                   "created_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:12",
186     *                   "updated_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:12"
187     *                 }
188     *             },
189     *             {
190     *               "type": "
sami_config_milestone",
191     *               "id": "2",
192     *               "attributes": {
193     *                 "sami_config_id": 1,
194     *                 "milestone_category
": "BNO",
195     *                 "milestone_code": "
```

```

195 i1000",
196     *
milestone_relative_range_start": 24,
197     *
milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
198     *
"milestone_frequency
": 5,
199     *
"created_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:16",
200     *
"updated_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:16"
201     *
}
202     *
}
203     *
]
204     *
}
205     *
}
206     *
}
207     *
}
208 */
209 /**
210     * @api {delete} /api/sami_config/{id
} Delete
211     * @apiGroup SamiConfig
212     * @apiName SamiConfigDelete
213     * @apiDescription Delete the given entity.
214     * @apiParam {integer} id Entity id.
215     * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
216     * HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
217     * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
218     * HTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
219     */
220     protected function getTransformer():
ResourceTransformerInterface
221     {
222         return new SamiConfigTransformer();
223     }
224
225     protected function getRepository(): BaseRepository
226     {
227         return new SamiConfigRepository();
228     }
229
230     /**
231     * @api {post} /api/sami_config Store
232     * @apiGroup SamiConfig
233     * @apiName SamiConfigStore
234     * @apiDescription Store a new entity.

```

```

235 * @apiExample Example-Request:
236 * {
237 *     "data":
238 *     {
239 *         "type": "sami_config",
240 *         "attributes": {
241 *             "project_id": 1,
242 *             "factors": {
243 *                 "sample key": "sample value"
244 *             },
245 *             "type": "segmentation",
246 *             "name": "Name",
247 *             "starting_date": "2012-01-01",
248 *             "ending_date": "2017-01-01",
249 *             "category": "BNO",
250 *             "code": "i1000",
251 *             "relative_range_start": 24,
252 *             "relative_range_end": 12
253 *         }
254 *     }
255 * }
256 * @apiSuccess {object} data The created
entity.
257 * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
258 * HTTP/1.1 201 Created
259 * {
260 *     "data":
261 *     {
262 *         "type": "sami_config",
263 *         "id": "1",
264 *         "attributes": {
265 *             "project_id": 1,
266 *             "factors": {
267 *                 "sample key": "sample value"
268 *             },
269 *             "type": "segmentation",
270 *             "name": "Name",
271 *             "starting_date": "2012-01-01",
272 *             "ending_date": "2017-01-01",
273 *             "category": "BNO",
274 *             "code": "i1000",
275 *             "relative_range_start": 24,
276 *             "relative_range_end": 12,
277 *             "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
278 *             "updated_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
279 *             "milestones": {
280 *                 "data": [

```

```
281     *                               {
282     *                               "type": "
sami_config_milestone",
283     *                               "id": "1",
284     *                               "attributes": {
285     *                                   "sami_config_id": 1,
286     *                                   "milestone_category
": "BNO",
287     *                                   "milestone_code": "
i1000",
288     *                                   "
milestone_relative_range_start": 24,
289     *                                   "
milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
290     *                                   "milestone_frequency
": 5,
291     *                                   "created_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:12",
292     *                                   "updated_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:12"
293     *                               }
294     *                               },
295     *                               {
296     *                               "type": "
sami_config_milestone",
297     *                               "id": "2",
298     *                               "attributes": {
299     *                                   "sami_config_id": 1,
300     *                                   "milestone_category
": "BNO",
301     *                                   "milestone_code": "
i1000",
302     *                                   "
milestone_relative_range_start": 24,
303     *                                   "
milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
304     *                                   "milestone_frequency
": 5,
305     *                                   "created_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:16",
306     *                                   "updated_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:16"
307     *                               }
308     *                               }
309     *                               ]
310     *                               }
311     *                               }
```

```

312     *     }
313     *     }
314     */
315     public function store(SamiConfigPostRequest $request)
316     {
317         $data = $request->input('data');
318         $model = $this->getRepository()->store($data['
attributes']);
319         return $this->getItemResponse($model, Response::
HTTP_CREATED);
320     }
321
322     /**
323     * @api                {patch} /api/sami_config/{id
} Update
324     * @apiGroup           SamiConfig
325     * @apiName            SamiConfigUpdate
326     * @apiDescription     Update an entity.
327     * @apiParam           {integer} id Entity id.
328     * @apiExample        Example-Request:
329     *     {
330     *         "data":
331     *         {
332     *             "type": "sami_config",
333     *             "id": "1",
334     *             "attributes": {
335     *                 "project_id": 1,
336     *                 "factors": {
337     *                     "sample key": "sample value"
338     *                 },
339     *                 "type": "segmentation",
340     *                 "name": "Name",
341     *                 "starting_date": "2012-01-01",
342     *                 "ending_date": "2017-01-01",
343     *                 "category": "BNO",
344     *                 "code": "i1001",
345     *                 "relative_range_start": 24,
346     *                 "relative_range_end": 12
347     *             }
348     *         }
349     *     }
350     * @apiSuccess         {object} data The entity.
351     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
352     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
353     *     {
354     *         "data":
355     *         {

```

```
356     *           "type": "sami_config",
357     *           "id": "1",
358     *           "attributes": {
359     *               "project_id": 1,
360     *               "factors": {
361     *                   "sample key": "sample value"
362     *               },
363     *               "type": "segmentation",
364     *               "name": "Name",
365     *               "starting_date": "2012-01-01",
366     *               "ending_date": "2017-01-01",
367     *               "category": "BNO",
368     *               "code": "i1001",
369     *               "relative_range_start": 24,
370     *               "relative_range_end": 12,
371     *               "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
372     *               "updated_at": "2019-07-24 06:48:26",
373     *               "milestones": {
374     *                   "data": [
375     *                       {
376     *                           "type": "
sami_config_milestone",
377     *                           "id": "1",
378     *                           "attributes": {
379     *                               "sami_config_id": 1,
380     *                               "milestone_category
": "BNO",
381     *                               "milestone_code": "
i1000",
382     *                               "
milestone_relative_range_start": 24,
383     *                               "
milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
384     *                               "milestone_frequency
": 5,
385     *                               "created_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:12",
386     *                               "updated_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:12"
387     *                           }
388     *                       },
389     *                   {
390     *                       "type": "
sami_config_milestone",
391     *                       "id": "2",
392     *                       "attributes": {
393     *                           "sami_config_id": 1,
```

```

394     *                                     "milestone_category
": "BNO",
395     *                                     "milestone_code": "
i1000",
396     *                                     "
milestone_relative_range_start": 24,
397     *                                     "
milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
398     *                                     "milestone_frequency
": 5,
399     *                                     "created_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:16",
400     *                                     "updated_at": "2019-
07-25 07:19:16"
401     *                                     }
402     *                                     }
403     *                                     ]
404     *                                     }
405     *                                     }
406     *                                     }
407     *                                     }
408     */
409     public function update($id, SamiConfigPutRequest
$request)
410     {
411         $data = $request->input('data');
412         $model = $this->getRepository()->update($id,
$data['attributes']);
413         return $this->getItemResponse($model);
414     }
415     protected function getFilterInfo(Request $request)
416     {
417         $filters = [
418             'project_id' => $request->get('project_id'),
419             'type' => $request->get('type'),
420         ];
421
422         return $filters;
423     }
424
425     /**
426     * @api                                     {get} /api/sami_config/
categories List
427     * @apiGroup                               SamiConfigCategories
428     * @apiName                               SamiConfigCategoriesList
429     * @apiDescription                         List all categories.
430     * @apiSuccess                             {object} data The categories.

```

```
431 * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
432 *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
433 *     {
434 *         [
435 *             {
436 *                 "value": "BNO",
437 *                 "name": "BNO"
438 *             },
439 *             {
440 *                 "value": "OENO",
441 *                 "name": "OENO"
442 *             },
443 *             {
444 *                 "value": "ATC",
445 *                 "name": "ATC"
446 *             },
447 *             {
448 *                 "value": "Death",
449 *                 "name": "Death"
450 *             }
451 *         ]
452 *     }
453 */
454 public function getCategories()
455 {
456     $categories = SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORIES;
457     $categoriesArray = [];
458     foreach ($categories as $categorie) {
459         $categoriesArray[] = [
460             'value' => $categorie, 'name' =>
461             $categorie,
462         ];
463     }
464     return $categoriesArray;
465 }
466 }
467
```

```

1  <?php
2
3  namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
4
5  use App\Repositories\AggregatedDataRepository;
6  use App\Transformers\Api\AggregatedDataTransformer;
7  use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Controllers\
    BaseResourceController;
8  use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
    BaseRepository;
9  use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
    ResourceTransformerInterface;
10 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
11
12 class AggregatedDataController extends
    BaseResourceController
13 {
14     protected function getTransformer():
    ResourceTransformerInterface
15     {
16         return new AggregatedDataTransformer();
17     }
18
19     protected function getRepository(): BaseRepository
20     {
21         return new AggregatedDataRepository();
22     }
23
24     /**
25      * @api           {get} /api/aggregated_data
    List
26      * @apiGroup     AggregatedData
27      * @apiName      AggregatedDataList
28      * @apiDescription List all entity.
29      * @apiParam     {integer} limit Number of
    items
30      * @apiParam     {string} orderby The field
    name to order by
31      * @apiParam     {string} sortorder Ordering
    direction (asc|desc)
32      * @apiParam     {string} project_id The id of
    the project
33      * @apiParam     {string} year Year filter
34      * @apiParam     {string} machine_name The type
    of the data (gender/atc/bno...)
35      * @apiParam     {string} value The value for
    type of data (male|i2160...)

```

```

36     * @apiParam          {integer} level Group by the
    first n (level) characters of value
37     * @apiParam          {string} category Filter
    machine_name-s, with categories (ICD|ICPM|ATC|...)
38     * @apiSuccess        {object} data The entity.
39     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
40     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
41     *     {
42     *         "data": [
43     *             {
44     *                 "type": "aggregatedData",
45     *                 "id": "1",
46     *                 "attributes": {
47     *                     "project_id": 1,
48     *                     "machine_name": "
    patient_demography_age",
49     *                     "value": "0-19",
50     *                     "count": 419
51     *                 }
52     *             },
53     *             {
54     *                 "type": "aggregatedData",
55     *                 "id": "2",
56     *                 "attributes": {
57     *                     "project_id": 1,
58     *                     "machine_name": "
    patient_demography_age",
59     *                     "value": "20-29",
60     *                     "count": 70
61     *                 }
62     *             }
63     *         ]
64     *     }
65     */
66     public function data(Request $request)
67     {
68         $limit = $request->get('limit') ?? null;
69         $orderBy = $request->get('orderby', 'machine_name'
    );
70         $sortOrder = $request->get('sortorder', 'asc');
71         $orderInfo = ['order_by' => $orderBy, 'sort_order'
    => $sortOrder];
72
73         $entities = $this->repository->
    getFilteredOrderedWithLimit(
74             $this->getFilterInfo($request),
75             $orderInfo,

```

```

76         $limit
77     );
78
79     return $this->getCollectionResponse($entities);
80 }
81
82 /**
83  * @api {get} /api/aggregated_data/
export Export
84  * @apiGroup AggregatedData
85  * @apiName AggregatedDataExport
86  * @apiDescription Export filtered data to csv.
87  * @apiParam {integer} limit Number of
items
88  * @apiParam {string} orderby The field
name to order by
89  * @apiParam {string} sortorder Ordering
direction (asc|desc)
90  * @apiParam {string} project_id The id of
the project
91  * @apiParam {string} year Year filter
92  * @apiParam {string} machine_name The
type of the data (gender|atc|bno...)
93  * @apiParam {string} value The value for
type of data (male|i2160...)
94  * @apiParam {integer} level Group by the
first n (level) characters of value
95  * @apiParam {string} category Filter
machine_name-s, with categories (ICD|ICPM|ATC|...)
96  * @apiSuccess CSV file
97  * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
98  * HTTP/1.1 200 OK
99  * CSV file
100  * 1,patient_demography_age,0-19,191
101  * 1,patient_demography_age,100,16
102  * 1,patient_demography_age,20-29,32
103  * 1,patient_demography_age,30-39,32
104  */
105 public function export(Request $request)
106 {
107     $limit = $request->get('limit') ?? null;
108     $orderBy = $request->get('orderby', 'machine_name
');
109     $sortOrder = $request->get('sortorder', 'asc');
110     $orderInfo = ['order_by' => $orderBy, 'sort_order
' => $sortOrder];
111

```

```
112         $entities = $this->repository->
getFilteredOrderedWithLimit(
113             $this->getFilterInfo($request),
114             $orderInfo,
115             $limit
116         );
117
118         $transformer = $this->getTransformer();
119         $lines = $this->fractal->collection($entities,
$transformer, $transformer::getResourceKey());
120
121         $headers = [
122             "Content-type" => "text/csv",
123             "Content-Disposition" => "attachment;
filename=aggregated_data.csv",
124             "Pragma" => "no-cache",
125             "Cache-Control" => "must-revalidate, post-
check=0, pre-check=0",
126             "Expires" => "0",
127         ];
128
129         $callback = function () use ($lines) {
130             $file = fopen('php://output', 'w');
131
132             foreach (($lines['data'] ?? null) as $line) {
133                 fputcsv($file, $line['attributes'] ??
null);
134             }
135
136             fclose($file);
137         };
138
139         return response()->stream($callback, 200,
$headers);
140     }
141
142     protected function getFilterInfo(Request $request)
143     {
144         $filters = [];
145
146         foreach ($this->repository->getAllowedFilters()
as $filter) {
147             $filters[$filter] = $request->get($filter);
148         }
149
150         $filters['level'] = $request->get('level') ??
null;
```

File - /project/app/Http/Controllers/Api/AggregatedDataController.php

```
151     $filters['level'] = is_numeric($filters['level']
    ]) ? $filters['level'] : null;
152
153     $filters['category'] = $request->get('category'
    ) ?? null;
154
155     return $filters;
156 }
157 }
158
```

```

1  <?php
2
3  namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
4
5  use App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnCategory\
    ColumnCategoryPostRequest;
6  use App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnCategory\
    ColumnCategoryPutRequest;
7  use App\Repositories\ColumnCategoryRepository;
8  use App\Transformers\Api\
    ColumnCategoryHierarchyTransformer;
9  use App\Transformers\Api\ColumnCategoryTransformer;
10 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Controllers\
    BaseResourceController;
11 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
    BaseRepository;
12 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\Fractal;
13 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
    ResourceTransformerInterface;
14 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
15 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
16 use League\Fractal\Serializer\ArraySerializer;
17
18 class ColumnCategoryController extends
    BaseResourceController
19 {
20     /**
21      * @api           {get} /api/column_category
    List
22      * @apiGroup    ColumnCategory
23      * @apiName     ColumnCategoryList
24      * @apiDescription List all entity.
25      * @apiParam    {integer} page Page number
26      * @apiParam    {integer} limit Number of
    items per page
27      * @apiParam    {string} orderby The field
    name to order by
28      * @apiParam    {string} sortorder Ordering
    direction (asc/desc)
29      * @apiSuccess  {object} data The entity.
30      * @apiSuccess  {object} meta Pagination
    information.
31      * @apiSuccess  {object} links Pagination
    links.
32      * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
33      *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
34      *     {

```

```

35     *         "data": [
36     *             {
37     *                 "type": "column_category",
38     *                 "id": "1",
39     *                 "attributes": {
40     *                     "parent_id": 1,
41     *                     "lft": 1,
42     *                     "rgt": 1,
43     *                     "depth": 1,
44     *                     "name": "sample string",
45     *                     "machine_name": "sample string",
46     *                     "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
47     *                     "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
48     *                 }
49     *             }
50     *         ],
51     *         "meta": {
52     *             "pagination": {
53     *                 "total": 1,
54     *                 "count": 1,
55     *                 "per_page": 50,
56     *                 "current_page": 1,
57     *                 "total_pages": 1
58     *             }
59     *         },
60     *         "links": {
61     *             "self": "http://localhost/api/
column_category?limit=50&page=1",
62     *             "first": "http://localhost/api/
column_category?limit=50&page=1",
63     *             "last": "http://localhost/api/
column_category?limit=50&page=1"
64     *         }
65     *     }
66     */
67     /**
68     * @api          {get} /api/column_category/{id
} Show
69     * @apiGroup    ColumnCategory
70     * @apiName     ColumnCategoryShow
71     * @apiDescription Show an entity.
72     * @apiParam    {integer} id Entity id.
73     * @apiSuccess  {object} data The entity.
74     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
75     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
76     *     {
77     *         "data":

```

```

78     *         {
79     *         "type": "column_category",
80     *         "id": "1",
81     *         "attributes": {
82     *             "parent_id": 1,
83     *             "lft": 1,
84     *             "rgt": 1,
85     *             "depth": 1,
86     *             "name": "sample string",
87     *             "machine_name": "sample string",
88     *             "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
89     *             "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
90     *         }
91     *     }
92     * }
93 */
94 /**
95  * @api {delete} /api/column_category
  /{id} Delete
96  * @apiGroup ColumnCategory
97  * @apiName ColumnCategoryDelete
98  * @apiDescription Delete the given entity.
99  * @apiParam {integer} id Entity id.
100 * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
101 *     HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
102 * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
103 *     HTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
104 */
105 protected function getTransformer():
ResourceTransformerInterface
106 {
107     return new ColumnCategoryTransformer();
108 }
109
110 protected function getRepository(): BaseRepository
111 {
112     return new ColumnCategoryRepository();
113 }
114
115 /**
116  * @api {post} /api/column_category
  Store
117  * @apiGroup ColumnCategory
118  * @apiName ColumnCategoryStore
119  * @apiDescription Store a new entity.
120  * @apiExample Example-Request:
121  *     {

```

```

122     *         "data":
123     *         {
124     *             "type": "column_category",
125     *             "attributes": {
126     *                 "parent_id": 1,
127     *                 "lft": 1,
128     *                 "rgt": 1,
129     *                 "depth": 1,
130     *                 "name": "sample string",
131     *                 "machine_name": "sample string",
132     *             }
133     *         }
134     *     }
135     * @apiSuccess {object} data The created
entity.
136     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
137     *     HTTP/1.1 201 Created
138     *     {
139     *         "data":
140     *         {
141     *             "type": "column_category",
142     *             "id": "1",
143     *             "attributes": {
144     *                 "parent_id": 1,
145     *                 "lft": 1,
146     *                 "rgt": 1,
147     *                 "depth": 1,
148     *                 "name": "sample string",
149     *                 "machine_name": "sample string",
150     *                 "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
151     *                 "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
152     *             }
153     *         }
154     *     }
155     */
156     public function store(ColumnCategoryPostRequest
$request)
157     {
158         $data = $request->input('data');
159         $model = $this->getRepository()->store($data['
attributes']);
160         return $this->getItemResponse($model, Response::
HTTP_CREATED);
161     }
162
163     /**
164     * @api {patch} /api/column_category

```

```

164 /{id} Update
165 * @apiGroup      ColumnCategory
166 * @apiName      ColumnCategoryUpdate
167 * @apiDescription Update an entity.
168 * @apiParam      {integer} id Entity id.
169 * @apiExample    Example-Request:
170 *      {
171 *          "data":
172 *          {
173 *              "type": "column_category",
174 *              "id": "1",
175 *              "attributes": {
176 *                  "parent_id": 1,
177 *                  "lft": 1,
178 *                  "rgt": 1,
179 *                  "depth": 1,
180 *                  "name": "sample string",
181 *                  "machine_name": "sample string",
182 *              }
183 *          }
184 *      }
185 * @apiSuccess    {object} data The entity.
186 * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
187 *      HTTP/1.1 200 OK
188 *      {
189 *          "data":
190 *          {
191 *              "type": "column_category",
192 *              "id": "1",
193 *              "attributes": {
194 *                  "parent_id": 1,
195 *                  "lft": 1,
196 *                  "rgt": 1,
197 *                  "depth": 1,
198 *                  "name": "sample string",
199 *                  "machine_name": "sample string",
200 *                  "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
201 *                  "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
202 *              }
203 *          }
204 *      }
205 */
206 public function update($id, ColumnCategoryPutRequest
    $request)
207 {
208     $data = $request->input('data');
209     $model = $this->getRepository()->update($id,

```

```

209 $data['attributes']);
210     return $this->getItemResponse($model);
211 }
212
213
214 /**
215  *
216  * @api           {get} /api/column_category/
217  hierarchy Hierarchy
218  * @apiGroup     ColumnCategory
219  * @apiName      ColumnCategoryListHierarchy
220  * @apiDescription List all entity in
221  hierarchical form.
222  * @apiSuccess   {object} data The entity list
223  * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
224  {
225     "data": [
226         {
227             "name": "Identifier",
228             "machine_name": "identifier",
229             "items": [
230                 {
231                     "name": "TAJ",
232                     "machine_name": "
233 identifier_patient_id",
234                     "items": []
235                 },
236                 {
237                     "name": "Karton",
238                     "machine_name": "
239 identifier_medical_record",
240                     "items": []
241                 },
242                 {
243                     "name": "Eset",
244                     "machine_name": "
245 identifier_medical_case",
246                     "items": []
247                 },
248                 {
249                     "name": "Egyéb",
250                     "machine_name": "
251 identifier_miscellaneous",
252                     "items": []
253                 }
254             ]
255         }
256     ]
257 }

```

```
249         ]
250     },
251     {
252         "name": "Patient",
253         "machine_name": "patient",
254         "items": [
255             {
256                 "name": "Demográfia",
257                 "machine_name": "
patient_demography",
258                 "items": [
259                     {
260                         "name": "Születési idő",
261                         "machine_name": "
patient_demography_date_of_birth",
262                         "items": []
263                     },
264                     {
265                         "name": "Kor",
266                         "machine_name": "
patient_demography_age",
267                         "items": []
268                     },
269                     {
270                         "name": "Nem",
271                         "machine_name": "
patient_demography_gender",
272                         "items": []
273                     },
274                     {
275                         "name": "Lakóhely megye",
276                         "machine_name": "
patient_demography_residence_county",
277                         "items": []
278                     },
279                     {
280                         "name": "Egyéb",
281                         "machine_name": "
patient_demography_miscellaneous",
282                         "items": []
283                     }
284                 ]
285             }
286         ]
287     }
288 ]
289 }
```

```
290     *
291     */
292
293     public function hierarchy()
294     {
295         $data = $this->repository->getRoot(
ColumnCategoryRepository::ROOT_NAME);
296         $fractal = new Fractal(new ArraySerializer());
297         $resource = $fractal->item(
298             $data,
299             new ColumnCategoryHierarchyTransformer(),
300             ColumnCategoryHierarchyTransformer::
getResourceKey()
301         );
302         return response()->json(['data' => $resource]);
303     }
304     protected function getFilterInfo(Request $request)
305     {
306         $filters = [
307             'parent_id' => $request->get('parent_id'),
308             'lft' => $request->get('lft'),
309             'rgt' => $request->get('rgt'),
310             'depth' => $request->get('depth'),
311             'name' => $request->get('name'),
312             'machine_name' => $request->get('machine_name
'),
313         ];
314         return $filters;
315     }
316 }
317
```

```

1  <?php
2
3  namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
4
5  use App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnDefinition\
    ColumnDefinitionPostRequest;
6  use App\Http\Requests\Api\ColumnDefinition\
    ColumnDefinitionPutRequest;
7  use App\Repositories\ColumnDefinitionRepository;
8  use App\Repositories\FileRepository;
9  use App\Transformers\Api\ColumnDefinitionTransformer;
10 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Controllers\
    BaseResourceController;
11 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
    BaseRepository;
12 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
    ResourceTransformerInterface;
13 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
14 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
15 use Illuminate\Support\Arr;
16
17 class ColumnDefinitionController extends
    BaseResourceController
18 {
19     /**
20      * @api           {get} /api/column_definition
    List
21      * @apiGroup     ColumnDefinition
22      * @apiName       ColumnDefinitionList
23      * @apiDescription List all entity.
24      * @apiParam     {integer} page Page number
25      * @apiParam     {integer} limit Number of
    items per page
26      * @apiParam     {string} orderby The field
    name to order by
27      * @apiParam     {string} sortorder Ordering
    direction (asc|desc)
28      * @apiSuccess   {object} data The entity.
29      * @apiSuccess   {object} meta Pagination
    information.
30      * @apiSuccess   {object} links Pagination
    links.
31      * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
32      *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
33      *     {
34      *         "data": [
35      *             {

```

```

36     *         "type": "column_definition",
37     *         "id": "1",
38     *         "attributes": {
39     *             "column_number": "0",
40     *             "column_name": "sample string",
41     *             "category": "category_machine_name",
42     *             "project_id": 1,
43     *             "file_id": 1,
44     *             "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
45     *             "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
46     *         }
47     *     }
48     * ],
49     *     "meta": {
50     *         "pagination": {
51     *             "total": 1,
52     *             "count": 1,
53     *             "per_page": 50,
54     *             "current_page": 1,
55     *             "total_pages": 1
56     *         }
57     *     },
58     *     "links": {
59     *         "self": "http://localhost/api/
column_definition?limit=50&page=1",
60     *         "first": "http://localhost/api/
column_definition?limit=50&page=1",
61     *         "last": "http://localhost/api/
column_definition?limit=50&page=1"
62     *     }
63     * }
64 */
65 /**
66  * @api           {get} /api/column_definition/{
id} Show
67  * @apiGroup      ColumnDefinition
68  * @apiName       ColumnDefinitionShow
69  * @apiDescription Show an entity.
70  * @apiParam      {integer} id Entity id.
71  * @apiSuccess    {object} data The entity.
72  * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
73  *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
74  *     {
75  *         "data":
76  *         {
77  *             "type": "column_definition",
78  *             "id": "1",

```

```

79     *           "attributes": {
80     *               "column_number": "0",
81     *               "column_name": "sample string",
82     *               "category": "category_machine_name",
83     *               "project_id": 1,
84     *               "file_id": 1,
85     *               "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
86     *               "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
87     *           }
88     *       }
89     *   }
90 */
91 /**
92  * @api           {delete} /api/
column_definition/{id} Delete
93  * @apiGroup      ColumnDefinition
94  * @apiName       ColumnDefinitionDelete
95  * @apiDescription Delete the given entity.
96  * @apiParam      {integer} id Entity id.
97  * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
98  *     HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
99  * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
100 *     HTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
101 */
102 protected function getTransformer():
ResourceTransformerInterface
103 {
104     return new ColumnDefinitionTransformer();
105 }
106
107 protected function getRepository(): BaseRepository
108 {
109     return new ColumnDefinitionRepository();
110 }
111 /**
112  * @codingStandardsIgnoreStart
113  */
114 /**
115  * @api           {post} /api/column_definition
Store
116  * @apiGroup      ColumnDefinition
117  * @apiName       ColumnDefinitionStore
118  * @apiDescription Store a new entity.
119  * @apiExample    Example-Request:
120  *     {
121  *         "data":
122  *     {

```

```

123     *           "type": "column_definition",
124     *           "attributes": {
125     *               "column_number": "0",
126     *               "column_name": "sample string",
127     *               "category": "category_machine_name",
128     *               "project_id": 1,
129     *               "file_id": 1,
130     *           }
131     *       }
132     *   }
133     * @apiSuccess           {object} data The created
entity.
134     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
135     *     HTTP/1.1 201 Created
136     *     {
137     *         "data":
138     *         {
139     *             "type": "column_definition",
140     *             "id": "1",
141     *             "attributes": {
142     *                 "column_number": "0",
143     *                 "column_name": "sample string",
144     *                 "category": "category_machine_name
", // use 'id', 'date' or 'code' for file types of 'icd
', 'atc' or 'icpm'
145     *                 "project_id": 1,
146     *                 "file_id": 1,
147     *                 "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
148     *                 "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
149     *             }
150     *         }
151     *     }
152     */
153     /**
154     * @codingStandardsIgnoreEnd
155     */
156     public function store(
157         ColumnDefinitionPostRequest $request,
158         FileRepository $fileRepository
159     ) {
160         $data = $request->input('data');
161         $data = $this->rewriteMachineNames(
$fileRepository, $data);
162         $model = $this->getRepository()->store($data['
attributes']);
163         return $this->getItemResponse($model, Response:::
HTTP_CREATED);

```

```

164     }
165
166     /**
167      * @codingStandardsIgnoreStart
168      */
169     /**
170      * @api {patch} /api/
column_definition/{id} Update
171      * @apiGroup ColumnDefinition
172      * @apiName ColumnDefinitionUpdate
173      * @apiDescription Update an entity.
174      * @apiParam {integer} id Entity id.
175      * @apiExample Example-Request:
176      * {
177      *     "data":
178      *     {
179      *         "type": "column_definition",
180      *         "id": "1",
181      *         "attributes": {
182      *             "column_number": "0",
183      *             "column_name": "sample string",
184      *             "category": "category_machine_name
", // use 'id', 'date' or 'code' for file types of 'icd
', 'atc' or 'icpm'
185      *             "project_id": 1,
186      *             "file_id": 1,
187      *         }
188      *     }
189      * }
190      * @apiSuccess {object} data The entity.
191      * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
192      * HTTP/1.1 200 OK
193      * {
194      *     "data":
195      *     {
196      *         "type": "column_definition",
197      *         "id": "1",
198      *         "attributes": {
199      *             "column_number": "0",
200      *             "column_name": "sample string",
201      *             "category": "category_machine_name",
202      *             "project_id": 1,
203      *             "file_id": 1,
204      *             "created_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
205      *             "updated_at": "2018-01-01 00:00:00",
206      *         }
207      *     }

```

```

208     *     }
209     */
210     /**
211     * @codingStandardsIgnoreEnd
212     */
213     public function update($id,
        ColumnDefinitionPutRequest $request, FileRepository
        $fileRepository)
214     {
215         $data = $request->input('data');
216         $data = $this->rewriteMachineNames(
        $fileRepository, $data);
217         $model = $this->getRepository()->update($id,
        $data['attributes']);
218         return $this->getItemResponse($model);
219     }
220     protected function getFilterInfo(Request $request)
221     {
222         $filters = [
223             'column_number' => $request->get('
        column_number'),
224             'column_name' => $request->get('column_name'
        ),
225             'category' => $request->get('category'),
226             'project_id' => $request->get('project_id'),
227             'file_id' => $request->get('file_id'),
228         ];
229         return $filters;
230     }
231
232     private function rewriteMachineNames(FileRepository
        $fileRepository, $data)
233     {
234         /** @var \App\Models\File $file */
235         $file = $fileRepository->getById($data['
        attributes']['file_id']);
236         if ($file->type !== FileRepository::PRIMARY_TYPE
        &&
237             in_array($file->type, FileRepository::
        DATA_TYPES)
238         ) {
239             switch ($data['attributes']['category']) {
240                 case 'id':
241                     $data = $this->rewriteIdCategory(
        $fileRepository, $data, $file);
242                     break;
243                 case 'date':

```

```
244         $data['attributes']['category'] = '
timestamp_date';
245         break;
246         case 'code':
247             $data = $this->rewriteCodeCategory(
248             $data, $file);
249             break;
250     }
251     return $data;
252 }
253
254 private function rewriteCodeCategory($data, \App\
Models\File $file)
255 {
256     switch ($file->type) {
257         case 'data-icd':
258             $data['attributes']['category'] =
259             Arr::first(ColumnDefinitionRepository
::ICD_MACHINE_NAMES);
260             break;
261         case 'data-atc':
262             $data['attributes']['category'] =
263             Arr::first(ColumnDefinitionRepository
::ATC_MACHINE_NAMES);
264             break;
265         case 'data-icpm':
266             $data['attributes']['category'] =
267             Arr::first(ColumnDefinitionRepository
::ICPM_MACHINE_NAMES);
268             break;
269         default:
270             abort(
271             Response::HTTP_UNPROCESSABLE_ENTITY,
272             'Invalid column type.'
273             );
274     }
275     return $data;
276 }
277
278 private function rewriteIdCategory(
279     FileRepository $fileRepository,
280     $data,
281     \App\Models\File $file
282 ) {
283     /** @var \App\Models\File $primaryFile */
284     $primaryFile = $fileRepository->
```

```
284 getPrimaryFileByFile($file);
285     $translatedCategory = $this->getRepository()
286         ->
        getIdentifierColumnNameByFile($primaryFile);
287     if ($translatedCategory === null) {
288         abort(
289             Response::HTTP_UNPROCESSABLE_ENTITY,
290             'Upload a demography file first.'
291         );
292     }
293     $data['attributes']['category'] =
    $translatedCategory;
294     return $data;
295 }
296 }
297
```

```

1  <?php
2
3  namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api;
4
5  use App\Http\Requests\Api\SamiConfigMilestone\
SamiConfigMilestonePostRequest;
6  use App\Http\Requests\Api\SamiConfigMilestone\
SamiConfigMilestonePutRequest;
7  use App\Repositories\SamiConfigMilestoneRepository;
8  use App\Transformers\Api\SamiConfigMilestoneTransformer;
9  use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Http\Controllers\
BaseResourceController;
10 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
BaseRepository;
11 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
ResourceTransformerInterface;
12 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
13 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
14
15 class SamiConfigMilestoneController extends
BaseResourceController
16 {
17     /**
18      * @api           {get} /api/
sami_config_milestone List
19      * @apiGroup     SamiConfig
20      * @apiName       SamiConfigList
21      * @apiDescription List all entity.
22      * @apiParam     {integer} page Page number
23      * @apiParam     {integer} limit Number of
items per page
24      * @apiParam     {string} orderby The field
name to order by
25      * @apiParam     {string} sortorder Ordering
direction (asc|desc)
26      * @apiSuccess   {object} data The entity.
27      * @apiSuccess   {object} meta Pagination
information.
28      * @apiSuccess   {object} links Pagination
links.
29      * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
30      *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
31      *     {
32      *         "data": [
33      *             {
34      *                 "type": "sami_config_milestone",
35      *                 "id": "1",

```

```

36     *         "attributes": {
37     *             "sami_config_id": 1,
38     *             "milestone_category": "BNO",
39     *             "milestone_code": "i1000",
40     *             "milestone_relative_range_start": 24,
41     *             "milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
42     *             "milestone_frequency": 5,
43     *             "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
44     *             "updated_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00"
45     *         }
46     *     }
47     * ],
48     *     "meta": {
49     *         "pagination": {
50     *             "total": 1,
51     *             "count": 1,
52     *             "per_page": 50,
53     *             "current_page": 1,
54     *             "total_pages": 1
55     *         }
56     *     },
57     *     "links": {
58     *         "self": "http://localhost/api/
sami_config_milestone?limit=50&page=1",
59     *         "first": "http://localhost/api/
sami_config_milestone?limit=50&page=1",
60     *         "last": "http://localhost/api/
sami_config_milestone?limit=50&page=1"
61     *     }
62     * }
63     */
64     /**
65     * @api           {get} /api/
sami_config_milestone/{id} Show
66     * @apiGroup      SamiConfig
67     * @apiName        SamiConfigShow
68     * @apiDescription Show an entity.
69     * @apiParam       {integer} id Entity id.
70     * @apiSuccess     {object} data The entity.
71     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
72     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
73     *     {
74     *         "data":
75     *         {
76     *             "type": "sami_config_milestone",
77     *             "id": "1",
78     *             "attributes": {

```

```

79     *         "sami_config_id": 1,
80     *         "milestone_category": "BNO",
81     *         "milestone_code": "i1000",
82     *         "milestone_relative_range_start": 24
83     *     },
84     *     "milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
85     *     "milestone_frequency": 5,
86     *     "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
87     *     "updated_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00"
88     *     }
89     * }
90 */
91 /**
92  * @api {delete} /api/
sami_config_milestone/{id} Delete
93  * @apiGroup SamiConfig
94  * @apiName SamiConfigDelete
95  * @apiDescription Delete the given entity.
96  * @apiParam {integer} id Entity id.
97  * @apiSuccessExample Success-Response:
98  *     HTTP/1.1 204 No Content
99  * @apiErrorExample Error-Response:
100  *     HTTP/1.1 404 Not Found
101 */
102 protected function getTransformer():
ResourceTransformerInterface
103 {
104     return new SamiConfigMilestoneTransformer();
105 }
106
107 protected function getRepository(): BaseRepository
108 {
109     return new SamiConfigMilestoneRepository();
110 }
111
112 /**
113  * @api {post} /api/
sami_config_milestone Store
114  * @apiGroup SamiConfigMilestone
115  * @apiName SamiConfigMilestoneStore
116  * @apiDescription Store a new entity.
117  * @apiExample Example-Request:
118  *     {
119  *         "data":
120  *             {
121  *                 "type": "sami_config_milestone",

```

```

122     *           "attributes": {
123     *               "sami_config_id": 1,
124     *               "milestone_category": "BNO",
125     *               "milestone_code": "i1000",
126     *               "milestone_relative_range_start": 24
127     *           },
128     *           "milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
129     *           "milestone_frequency": 5
130     *       }
131     *   }
132     * @apiSuccess {object} data The created
entity.
133     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
134     *     HTTP/1.1 201 Created
135     *     {
136     *         "data":
137     *         {
138     *             "type": "sami_config_milestone",
139     *             "id": "1",
140     *             "attributes": {
141     *                 "sami_config_id": 1,
142     *                 "milestone_category": "BNO",
143     *                 "milestone_code": "i1000",
144     *                 "milestone_relative_range_start": 24
145     *             },
146     *             "milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
147     *             "milestone_frequency": 5,
148     *             "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
149     *             "updated_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00"
150     *         }
151     *     }
152     */
153     public function store(SamiConfigMilestonePostRequest
$request)
154     {
155         $data = $request->input('data');
156         $model = $this->getRepository()->store($data['
attributes']);
157         return $this->getItemResponse($model, Response:::
HTTP_CREATED);
158     }
159
160     /**
161     * @api {patch} /api/
sami_config_milestone/{id} Update

```

```

162     * @apiGroup           SamiConfigMilestone
163     * @apiName           SamiConfigMilestoneUpdate
164     * @apiDescription   Update an entity.
165     * @apiParam         {integer} id Entity id.
166     * @apiExample      Example-Request:
167     *     {
168     *         "data":
169     *         {
170     *             "type": "sami_config_milestone",
171     *             "id": "1",
172     *             "attributes": {
173     *                 "sami_config_id": 1,
174     *                 "milestone_category": "BNO",
175     *                 "milestone_code": "i1000",
176     *                 "milestone_relative_range_start": 24
177     *                 "milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
178     *                 "milestone_frequency": 5,
179     *                 "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
180     *                 "updated_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00"
181     *             }
182     *         }
183     *     }
184     * @apiSuccess       {object} data The entity.
185     * @apiSuccessExample {json} Success-Response:
186     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
187     *     {
188     *         "data":
189     *         {
190     *             "type": "sami_config_milestone",
191     *             "id": "1",
192     *             "attributes": {
193     *                 "sami_config_id": 1,
194     *                 "milestone_category": "BNO",
195     *                 "milestone_code": "i1000",
196     *                 "milestone_relative_range_start": 24
197     *                 "milestone_relative_range_end": 12,
198     *                 "milestone_frequency": 5,
199     *                 "created_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00",
200     *                 "updated_at": "2019-07-23 10:00:00"
201     *             }
202     *         }
203     *     }
204     */
205     public function update($id,
SamiConfigMilestonePutRequest $request)

```

```
206     {
207         $data = $request->input('data');
208         $model = $this->getRepository()->update($id,
$data['attributes']);
209         return $this->getItemResponse($model);
210     }
211     protected function getFilterInfo(Request $request)
212     {
213         $filters = [
214             'sami_config_id' => $request->get('
sami_config_id'),
215         ];
216         return $filters;
217     }
218 }
219
```

```

1  <?php
2
3  namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api\Auth;
4
5  use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
6  use App\Repositories\UserRepository;
7  use Illuminate\Http\Response;
8
9  class VerificationController extends Controller
10 {
11     /**
12      * @var \App\Repositories\UserRepository
13      */
14     private $userRepository;
15
16     public function __construct(UserRepository
17 $userRepository)
18     {
19         $this->userRepository = $userRepository;
20     }
21     /**
22      * @api {get} /api/verify/{token} Verify
23      * @apiGroup Verify the email
24      * @apiErrorExample {json} Error-Response:
25      *     HTTP/1.1 401 Unauthorized Entity
26      *     {
27      *         "message": "Unsuccessfully password change
28      *     },
29      *     "status": 401,
30      *     }
31      * @apiSuccess {json} Response:
32      *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
33      *     {
34      *         "message": "Successfully password change
35      *     },
36      *     "status": 200,
37      *     }
38     */
39     public function verify($token)
40     {
41         $verifySuccess = $this->userRepository->
42 verifyEmail($token);
43         $text = $verifySuccess ? __('auth.verify_ok') :
44 __('auth.verify_fail');
45         $responseCode = $verifySuccess ? Response::HTTP_OK
46 : Response::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED;
47         return response()->json(

```

File - /project/app/Http/Controllers/Api/Auth/VerificationController.php

```
42         [
43             'message' => $text,
44             'status' => $responseCode
45         ],
46         $responseCode
47     );
48 }
49 }
50
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Http\Controllers\Api\Auth;
4
5 use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
6 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
7 use Illuminate\Foundation\Auth\ResetsPasswords;
8 use Illuminate\Http\Request;
9 use Illuminate\Support\Facades>Password;
10
11 class ResetPasswordController extends Controller
12 {
13     /*
14     |-----
15     | Password Reset Controller
16     |-----
17     |
18     | This controller is responsible for handling password
19     | reset requests
20     | and uses a simple trait to include this behavior.
21     | You're free to
22     | explore this trait and override any methods you wish
23     | to tweak.
24     |
25     */
26     use ResetsPasswords;
27
28     /**
29     * @api {post} /api/forgotten-password Forgotten PW
30     * @apiGroup Reset Password
31     * @apiParam {String} token Token that BE generate.
32     * @apiParam {String} email required attribute.
33     * @apiParam {String} password your new PW.
34     * @apiParam {String} password_confirmation must be
35     equal with 'password' attribute.
36     * @apiParamExample {json} Example-Request:
37     * {
38     *   "token": "abcdINVALIDTOKENabcd",
39     *   "email": "user@example.com",
40     *   "password": "12345",
41     *   "password_confirmation": "12345",
42     * }
43     * @apiErrorExample {json} Error-Response:
44     * HTTP/1.1 401 Unauthorized Entity
```

```
42     *     {
43     *         "message": "Unsuccessfully password change
. ",
44     *         "status": 401,
45     *         "detail": "passwords.token"
46     *     }
47     * @apiSuccess {json} Response:
48     *     HTTP/1.1 200 OK
49     *     {
50     *         "message": "Successfully password change
. ",
51     *         "status": 200,
52     *         "detail": "passwords.users"
53     *     }
54     */
55     public function reset(Request $request)
56     {
57         $request->validate($this->rules(), $this->
validationErrorMessages());
58         $response = $this->broker()->reset(
59             $this->credentials($request),
60             function ($user, $password) {
61                 $this->resetPassword($user, $password);
62             }
63         );
64         $isSuccess = $response == Password::PASSWORD_RESET
;
65         $msg = $isSuccess ? __('auth.
forgot_password_success') : __('auth.
forgot_password_unsuccess');
66         $responseCode = $isSuccess ? Response::HTTP_OK :
Response::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED;
67         return response()->json(
68             [
69                 'message' => $msg,
70                 'status' => $responseCode,
71                 'detail' => $response
72             ],
73             $responseCode
74         );
75     }
76 }
77
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Jobs;
4
5 use App\Models\File;
6 use App\Repositories\ColumnDefinitionRepository;
7 use App\Utils\Validation\State\AbstractState;
8 use Illuminate\Bus\Queueable;
9 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
10 use Illuminate\Queue\InteractsWithQueue;
11 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
12 use Illuminate\Foundation\Bus\Dispatchable;
13 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Storage;
14
15 class ValidateFile implements ShouldQueue
16 {
17     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithQueue, Queueable,
18     SerializesModels;
19
20     /**
21      * The number of times the job may be attempted.
22      *
23      * @var int
24      */
25     public $tries = 6;
26
27     /**
28      * The number of seconds to wait before retrying the
29      * job.
30      *
31      * @var int
32      */
33     public $retryAfter = 10;
34
35     /**
36      * @var \App\Models\File
37      */
38     private $file;
39
40     /**
41      * @var integer
42      */
43     private $chunkSize;
44
45     /**
46      * @var \App\Models\ColumnDefinition[]|\Illuminate\
47     Database\Eloquent\Collection
```

```
45     */
46     private $columnDefinitions;
47
48     /**
49      * @var \App\Utils\Validation\State\AbstractState
50      */
51     private $state;
52
53     /**
54      * @var \App\Repositories\ColumnDefinitionRepository
55      */
56     private $columnDefinitionRepository;
57
58     /**
59      * Create a new job instance.
60      *
61      * @return void
62      */
63     public function __construct(
64         File $file,
65         AbstractState $state,
66         ColumnDefinitionRepository
67         $columnDefinitionRepository
68     ) {
69         $this->file = $file;
70         $this->chunkSize = config('app.
71         validation_chunk_size');
72         $this->state = $state;
73         $this->columnDefinitionRepository =
74         $columnDefinitionRepository;
75     }
76
77     /**
78      * Execute the job.
79      *
80      * @return void
81      */
82     public function handle()
83     {
84         $this->state->publishInfo(['info' => 'Processing
85         started', 'file_id' => $this->file->id,]);
86         $this->state->flushState();
87
88         $this->columnDefinitions =
89         $this->columnDefinitionRepository->
90         getOrderedListByFileId($this->file->id);
91     }
92 }
```

```
87     $filepath = Storage::disk('local')->path($this->
file->path . $this->file->file_name);
88     $handle = fopen($filepath, 'r');
89     $chunkPointer = 1;
90     $linePointer = 1;
91     $dataChunk = [];
92     $bytesInChunk = 0;
93     $previousBytePointer = 0;
94     $columnNames = $this->getColumnNames();
95     $firstRow = true;
96     while (($data = fgetcsv($handle, 1000, config('
app.csv_separator')))) !== false) {
97         $bytePointer = ftell($handle);
98         $bytesInChunk += ($bytePointer -
$previousBytePointer);
99         $previousBytePointer = $bytePointer;
100        if ($firstRow) {
101            $firstRow = false;
102            continue;
103        }
104        $dataChunk[] = $data;
105        if ($chunkPointer === $this->chunkSize) {
106            ValidateChunk::dispatch(
107                $columnNames,
108                $linePointer,
109                $bytesInChunk,
110                $dataChunk,
111                $this->state
112            )->onQueue('default');
113
114            $linePointer += count($dataChunk);
115
116            $this->state->publishInfo([
117                'info' => 'Dispatching ' .
$linePointer . ' lines...',
118                'file_id' => $this->file->id,
119            ]);
120
121            $bytesInChunk = 0;
122            $chunkPointer = 0;
123            $dataChunk = [];
124        }
125
126        $chunkPointer++;
127    }
128    if (count($dataChunk)) {
129        ValidateChunk::dispatch(
```

File - /project/app/Jobs/ValidateFile.php

```
130         $columnNames,  
131         $linePointer,  
132         $bytesInChunk,  
133         $dataChunk,  
134         $this->state  
135     )->onQueue('default');  
136     }  
137  
138     $this->state->publishInfo(['info' => 'Processing  
finished', 'file_id' => $this->file->id,]);  
139     }  
140  
141     public function getColumnNames()  
142     {  
143         return $this->columnDefinitions->pluck('category'  
144     )->toArray();  
145     }  
146 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Jobs;
4
5 use App\Repositories\ColumnCategoryRepository;
6 use App\Utils\Aggregation\Aggregator;
7 use App\Utils\Validation\State\AbstractState;
8 use App\Utils\Validation\Validator;
9 use Illuminate\Bus\Queueable;
10 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
11 use Illuminate\Queue\InteractsWithQueue;
12 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
13 use Illuminate\Foundation\Bus\Dispatchable;
14
15 class ValidateChunk implements ShouldQueue
16 {
17     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithQueue, Queueable,
18     SerializesModels;
19
20     /**
21      * The number of times the job may be attempted.
22      *
23      * @var int
24      */
25     public $tries = 6;
26
27     /**
28      * The number of seconds to wait before retrying the
29      * job.
30      *
31      * @var int
32      */
33     public $retryAfter = 10;
34
35     /**
36      * Array with the machine names of the columns.
37      *
38      * @var array
39      */
40     private $columnConfig;
41
42     /**
43      * The data to be validated.
44      *
45      * @var array
46      */
47     private $dataChunk;
```

```
46
47  /**
48   * The line number of the data chunk first row.
49   *
50   * @var int
51   */
52  private $startLineNumber;
53
54  /**
55   * @var \App\Utils\Validation\State\AbstractState
56   */
57  private $state;
58
59  /**
60   * @var int
61   */
62  private $bytesInChunk;
63
64  /**
65   * Create a new job instance.
66   *
67   * @return void
68   */
69  public function __construct(
70      array $columnConfig,
71      int $startLineNumber,
72      int $bytesInChunk,
73      array $dataChunk,
74      AbstractState $state
75  ) {
76      $this->columnConfig = $columnConfig;
77      $this->dataChunk = $dataChunk;
78      $this->startLineNumber = $startLineNumber;
79      $this->state = $state;
80      $this->bytesInChunk = $bytesInChunk;
81  }
82
83  /**
84   * Execute the job.
85   *
86   * @return void
87   *
88   * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD.ElseExpression)
89   */
90  public function handle()
91  {
92      $validator = new Validator($this->columnConfig,
```

```
92 new ColumnCategoryRepository());
93     $aggregator = new Aggregator(
94         $this->state->getProjectId(),
95         $this->state->getFileId(),
96         $validator->getColumnConfig()
97     );
98     $dataToAggregate = [];
99     foreach ($this->dataChunk as $rowIndex => $row) {
100         /** @var \Illuminate\Validation\Validator
101         $result */
101         $result = $validator->validateRow($row);
102         $this->state->incrementProcessedRowsInChunk
103         ();
103         $this->state->incrementProcessedFieldsInChunk
104         (count($row));
104         if ($result->fails()) {
105             $this->state->
106             incrementRowsWithErrorsInChunk();
106             $this->state->
107             incrementFieldsWithErrorsInChunk(count($result->messages
108             ()));
107             $this->state->addRowErrors(
108                 $this->startLineNumber + $rowIndex,
109                 $result->messages(),
110                 $row
111             );
112         } else {
113             $dataToAggregate[] = $row;
114         }
115     }
116     if (count($dataToAggregate)) {
117         $aggregator->loadData($dataToAggregate);
118         AggregateChunk::dispatch($aggregator)->
119         onQueue('aggregation');
119     }
120     $this->state->incrementProcessedBytesInChunk(
121     $this->bytesInChunk);
121     $this->state->flushState();
122 }
123
124 protected function getArraySize($array)
125 {
126     $size = 0;
127     foreach ($array as $element) {
128         switch (is_array($element)) {
129             case true:
130                 $size += $this->getArraySize($element
```

File - /project/app/Jobs/ValidateChunk.php

```
130 );
131         break;
132     case false:
133         $size += mb_strlen($element, '8bit');
134         break;
135     }
136 }
137
138     return $size;
139 }
140 }
141
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Jobs;
4
5 use App\Utils\Aggregation\Aggregator;
6 use Illuminate\Bus\Queueable;
7 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
8 use Illuminate\Queue\InteractsWithQueue;
9 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
10 use Illuminate\Foundation\Bus\Dispatchable;
11
12 class AggregateChunk implements ShouldQueue
13 {
14     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithQueue, Queueable,
15     SerializesModels;
16     /**
17      * @var Aggregator
18      */
19     private $aggregator;
20
21     /**
22      * Create a new job instance.
23      *
24      * @return void
25      */
26     public function __construct(Aggregator $aggregator)
27     {
28         $this->aggregator = $aggregator;
29     }
30
31     /**
32      * Execute the job.
33      *
34      * @return void
35      */
36     public function handle()
37     {
38         $this->aggregator->run();
39     }
40 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Jobs;
4
5 use Illuminate\Bus\Queueable;
6 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
7 use Illuminate\Queue\InteractsWithQueue;
8 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
9 use Illuminate\Foundation\Bus\Dispatchable;
10 use Symfony\Component\Process\Exception\
    ProcessFailedException;
11 use Symfony\Component\Process\Process;
12
13 class CallMagicMethod implements ShouldQueue
14 {
15     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithQueue, Queueable,
        SerializesModels;
16
17     private $scriptPath;
18     private $projectId;
19     private $samiConfig;
20
21     // @TODO: change RUN_SCRIPT to actual script, magic.sh
        file can be deleted
22     private const RUN_SCRIPT = 'magic.sh';
23
24     /**
25      * Create a new job instance.
26      *
27      * @return void
28      */
29     public function __construct($projectId, $samiConfig)
30     {
31         $this->scriptPath = base_path(self::RUN_SCRIPT);
32         $this->projectId = $projectId;
33         $this->samiConfig = $samiConfig;
34     }
35
36     /**
37      * Execute the job.
38      *
39      * @return void
40      */
41     public function handle()
42     {
43         \Log::info('CallMagicMethod started');
44
```

File - /project/app/Jobs/CallMagicMethod.php

```
45     try {
46         $process = new Process([
47             $this->scriptPath,
48         ]);
49
50         $process->mustRun(function ($type, $data) {
51             if ($type !== Process::OUT) {
52                 \Log::error($data);
53             }
54         });
55     } catch (ProcessFailedException $exception) {
56         \Log::error($exception->getMessage());
57     }
58
59     \Log::info('CallMagicMethod finished');
60 }
61 }
62
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Jobs;
4
5 use App\Models\AtcData;
6 use App\Models\BnoData;
7 use App\Models\File;
8 use App\Models\OenoData;
9 use App\Repositories\FileRepository;
10 use Illuminate\Bus\Queueable;
11 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
12 use Illuminate\Queue\InteractsWithQueue;
13 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
14 use Illuminate\Foundation\Bus\Dispatchable;
15 use Storage;
16
17 class ImportCodeTable implements ShouldQueue
18 {
19     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithQueue, Queueable,
    SerializesModels;
20
21     protected $fileId;
22
23     /**
24      * Create a new job instance.
25      *
26      * @param int $fileId
27      * @throws \Exception
28      * @return void
29      */
30     public function __construct(int $fileId)
31     {
32         $this->fileId = $fileId;
33     }
34
35     /**
36      * Execute the job.
37      *
38      * @return void
39      */
40     public function handle()
41     {
42         $fileRepo = new FileRepository();
43         $file = $fileRepo->getByIdOrFail($this->fileId);
44
45         $this->importData($file);
46     }
```

```
47
48     /**
49      * Import data.
50      *
51      * @param File $file
52      */
53     protected function importData(File $file)
54     {
55         $handle = fopen(Storage::disk('local')->path($file
->path . $file->file_name), 'r');
56
57         while (!feof($handle)) {
58             $data = fgetcsv($handle, 0, config('app.
csv_separator'));
59
60             if (!$data) {
61                 continue;
62             }
63
64             $attributes = [
65                 'project_id' => $file->project_id,
66                 'code' => $data[0],
67                 'name' => $data[1],
68             ];
69
70             switch ($file->type) {
71                 case 'bno':
72                     BnoData::create($attributes);
73                     break;
74                 case 'atc':
75                     AtcData::create($attributes);
76                     break;
77                 case 'oeno':
78                     OenoData::create($attributes);
79                     break;
80             }
81         }
82
83         fclose($handle);
84     }
85 }
86
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Mail\Mailers;
4
5 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Mail;
6
7 abstract class MailerBase
8 {
9     protected $message;
10
11     public function send()
12     {
13         Mail::send($this->message);
14     }
15
16     public function queue()
17     {
18         Mail::queue($this->message);
19     }
20
21     public function later($delay)
22     {
23         Mail::later($delay, $this->message);
24     }
25 }
26
```

```
1 <?php
2 namespace App\Mail\Mailers;
3
4 use App\Mail\Mailables\User>PasswordLinkSender;
5 use App\Mail\Mailables\User\VerificationSender;
6 use App\User;
7
8 class UserMailer extends MailerBase
9 {
10     public function sendEmailConfirmationTo(User $user)
11     {
12         $this->message = new VerificationSender($user);
13
14         return $this;
15     }
16
17     public function sendPasswordLinkTo(User $user, $token)
18     {
19         $this->message = new PasswordLinkSender($user,
20 $token);
21
22         return $this;
23     }
24 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Mail\Mailables\User;
4
5 use App\User;
6 use Illuminate\Bus\Queueable;
7 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
8 use Illuminate\Mail\Mailable;
9 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
10
11 class PasswordLinkSender extends Mailable implements
    ShouldQueue
12 {
13     use Queueable, SerializesModels;
14
15     /**
16      * The order instance.
17      *
18      * @var User
19      */
20     public $user;
21
22     /**
23      * @var string
24      */
25     private $token;
26
27     /**
28      * Create a new message instance.
29      */
30     public function __construct(User $user, $token)
31     {
32         $this->user = $user;
33         $this->token = $token;
34     }
35
36     /**
37      * Build the message.
38      *
39      * @return $this
40      */
41     public function build()
42     {
43         return $this->view('emails.users.password')
44             ->with(['user' => $this->user, 'token' =>
45 $this->token])
46             ->to($this->user->email)
```

File - /project/app/Mail/Mailables/User/PasswordLinkSender.php

```
46         ->subject(config('mail.subject.password'))
47         ->from(config('mail.from.address'), config('
mail.from.name'));
48     }
49
50     /**
51      * @return string
52      */
53     public function getToken(): string
54     {
55         return $this->token;
56     }
57 }
58
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Mail\Mailables\User;
4
5 use App\User;
6 use Illuminate\Bus\Queueable;
7 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
8 use Illuminate\Mail\Mailable;
9 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
10
11 class VerificationSender extends Mailable implements
    ShouldQueue
12 {
13     use Queueable, SerializesModels;
14
15     /**
16      * The order instance.
17      *
18      * @var User
19      */
20     public $user;
21
22     /**
23      * Create a new message instance.
24      */
25     public function __construct(User $user)
26     {
27         $this->user = $user;
28     }
29
30     /**
31      * Build the message.
32      *
33      * @return $this
34      */
35     public function build()
36     {
37         return $this->view('emails.users.verification')
38             ->with(['user' => $this->user])
39             ->to($this->user->email)
40             ->subject(config('mail.subject.verification'))
41             ->from(config('mail.from.address'), config('
mail.from.name'));
42     }
43 }
44
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Rules;
4
5 use App\Repositories\ColumnCategoryRepository;
6 use Illuminate\Contracts\Validation\Rule;
7
8 class LeafColumnCategory implements Rule
9 {
10     /**
11      * Determine if the validation rule passes.
12      *
13      * @param string $attribute
14      * @param mixed $value
15      * @return bool
16      * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD.UnusedFormalParameter)
17      */
18     public function passes($attribute, $value)
19     {
20         if (in_array($value, ['id', 'date', 'code'])) {
21             return true;
22         }
23         $categoryRepo = new ColumnCategoryRepository();
24         $category = $categoryRepo->getByAttribute('
machine_name', $value);
25
26         if (empty($category)) {
27             return false;
28         }
29
30         return $category->isLeaf();
31     }
32
33     /**
34      * Get the validation error message.
35      *
36      * @return string
37      */
38     public function message()
39     {
40         return 'The Category ID is not the last';
41     }
42 }
43
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Rules;
4
5 use App\Repositories\ColumnCategoryRepository;
6 use Illuminate\Contracts\Validation\Rule;
7
8 class ColumnCategoryExists implements Rule
9 {
10     /**
11      * Determine if the validation rule passes.
12      *
13      * @param string $attribute
14      * @param mixed $value
15      * @return bool
16      * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD.UnusedFormalParameter)
17      */
18     public function passes($attribute, $value)
19     {
20         if (in_array($value, ['id', 'date', 'code'])) {
21             return true;
22         }
23         $categoryRepo = new ColumnCategoryRepository();
24         $category = $categoryRepo->getByAttribute('
machine_name', $value);
25
26         return !empty($category);
27     }
28
29     /**
30      * Get the validation error message.
31      *
32      * @return string
33      */
34     public function message()
35     {
36         return 'The Category ID is missing';
37     }
38 }
39
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Validation;
4
5 use App\Repositories\ColumnCategoryRepository;
6 use App\Utils\Validation\Exception\InvalidColumnCategory;
7 use App\Utils\Validation\Exception\MissingConfigParameter;
8 use Illuminate\Support\Arr;
9 use Validator as LaravelValidator;
10
11 class Validator
12 {
13     /**
14      * @var array
15      */
16     private $columnConfig;
17
18     /**
19      * @var \App\Repositories\ColumnCategoryRepository
20      */
21     private $columnCategoryRepository;
22
23     public function __construct(array $columnConfig,
24 ColumnCategoryRepository $columnCategoryRepository)
25     {
26         $this->columnConfig = $columnConfig;
27         $this->columnCategoryRepository =
28 $columnCategoryRepository;
29         $this->initColumns();
30     }
31
32     private function initColumns()
33     {
34         if (empty($this->columnConfig)) {
35             throw new MissingConfigParameter('There is no
36 machine names in column configuration.');
```

File - /project/app/Utils/Validation/Validator.php

```
42     }
43
44     public function validateRow(array $row)
45     {
46         return LaravelValidator::make($row, $this->
getRules());
47     }
48
49     public function getRules()
50     {
51         return Arr::pluck($this->columnConfig, 'validators
');
52     }
53
54     /**
55      * @return array
56      */
57     public function getColumnConfig(): array
58     {
59         return $this->columnConfig;
60     }
61 }
62
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Validation\State;
4
5 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Storage;
6 use League\Flysystem\FileNotFoundException;
7
8 class FileState extends AbstractState
9 {
10     private function getStateFileName()
11     {
12         return 'state_' . $this->projectId . '_' . $this->
fileId . '.json';
13     }
14
15     private function getInfoFileName()
16     {
17         return 'info_' . $this->projectId . '_' . $this->
fileId . '.json';
18     }
19
20     protected function loadState(): array
21     {
22         try {
23             $stateFile = Storage::disk('local')->get($this
->getStateFileName());
24         } catch (\Exception $exception) {
25             return [
26                 'processedBytes' => 0,
27                 'processedRows' => 0,
28                 'processedFields' => 0,
29                 'rowsWithError' => 0,
30                 'fieldsWithError' => 0,
31                 'errors' => [],
32             ];
33         }
34         return json_decode($stateFile, true);
35     }
36
37     protected function saveState(array $data): void
38     {
39         Storage::disk('local')->put($this->
getStateFileName(), json_encode($data));
40     }
41
42     public function publishInfo(array $data): void
43     {
```

File - /project/app/Utils/Validation/State/FileState.php

```
44     Storage::disk('local')->put($this->getInfoFileName  
    (), json_encode($data));  
45     }  
46 }  
47
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Validation\State;
4
5 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Redis;
6
7 class RedisState extends AbstractState
8 {
9     private function getChannelName()
10    {
11        return 'ws-user_' . $this->userID;
12    }
13
14    private function getStateKeyName()
15    {
16        return 'state-' . $this->projectId . '-' . $this->
fileId;
17    }
18
19    private function getInfoKeyName()
20    {
21        return 'info-' . $this->projectId . '-' . $this->
fileId;
22    }
23
24    protected function loadState(): array
25    {
26        $stateFile = Redis::get($this->getStateKeyName());
27
28        if (!$stateFile) {
29            return [
30                'processedBytes' => 0,
31                'processedRows' => 0,
32                'processedFields' => 0,
33                'rowsWithError' => 0,
34                'fieldsWithError' => 0,
35                'errors' => [],
36            ];
37        }
38
39        return json_decode($stateFile, true);
40    }
41
42    protected function saveState(array $data): void
43    {
44        Redis::setex($this->getStateKeyName(), 120,
json_encode($data));
```

```
45         Redis::publish($this->getChannelName(),
    json_encode([
46             'event' => $this->getStateKeyName(),
47             'data' => $data,
48         ]));
49     }
50
51     public function publishInfo(array $data): void
52     {
53         Redis::publish($this->getChannelName(),
    json_encode([
54             'event' => $this->getInfoKeyName(),
55             'data' => $data,
56         ]));
57     }
58 }
59
```

```
1 <?php
2
3
4 namespace App\Utils\Validation\State;
5
6 abstract class AbstractState
7 {
8     protected $fileSize = 0;
9
10    protected $processedBytesInChunk = 0;
11
12    protected $processedRowsInChunk = 0;
13
14    protected $processedFieldsInChunk = 0;
15
16    protected $rowsWithErrorsInChunk = 0;
17
18    protected $fieldsWithErrorsInChunk = 0;
19
20    protected $errorsInChunk = [];
21
22    protected $projectId;
23
24    protected $fileId;
25
26    protected $userId;
27
28    public function __construct(int $projectId, int
    $fileId, int $userId, int $fileSize)
29    {
30
31        $this->projectId = $projectId;
32        $this->fileId = $fileId;
33        $this->userId = $userId;
34        $this->fileSize = $fileSize;
35    }
36
37    public function incrementProcessedBytesInChunk(
    $increment = 1) :void
38    {
39        $this->processedBytesInChunk += $increment;
40    }
41
42    public function incrementProcessedRowsInChunk(
    $increment = 1) : void
43    {
44        $this->processedRowsInChunk += $increment;
```

```
45     }
46
47     public function incrementProcessedFieldsInChunk(
    $increment = 1) : void
48     {
49         $this->processedFieldsInChunk += $increment;
50     }
51
52     public function incrementRowsWithErrorsInChunk(
    $increment = 1) : void
53     {
54         $this->rowsWithErrorsInChunk += $increment;
55     }
56
57     public function incrementFieldsWithErrorsInChunk(
    $increment = 1) : void
58     {
59         $this->fieldsWithErrorsInChunk += $increment;
60     }
61
62     public function addRowErrors($lineNumber, $errors,
    $row)
63     {
64         $errorData = [
65             'line_number' => $lineNumber,
66             'error_messages' => $errors,
67             'row_data' => $row,
68         ];
69         $this->errorsInChunk[] = $errorData;
70     }
71
72     public function flushState() : void
73     {
74         $data = $this->loadState();
75
76         // Don't increment data after EOF.
77         if ($data['processedBytes'] >= $this->fileSize) {
78             $this->saveState($data);
79             return;
80         }
81
82         $data['project_id'] = $this->projectId;
83         $data['file_id'] = $this->fileId;
84         $data['file_size'] = $this->fileSize;
85         $data['processedBytes'] += $this->
    processedBytesInChunk;
86         $data['processedRows'] += $this->
```

```
86 processedRowsInChunk;
87     $data['processedFields'] += $this->
processedFieldsInChunk;
88     $data['rowsWithError'] += $this->
rowsWithErrorsInChunk;
89     $data['fieldsWithError'] += $this->
fieldsWithErrorsInChunk;
90     $data['errors'] = array_slice(array_merge($data['
errors'], $this->errorsInChunk), 0, 30);
91     $this->saveState($data);
92 }
93
94 public function getProjectId()
95 {
96     return $this->projectId;
97 }
98
99 public function getFileId()
100 {
101     return $this->fileId;
102 }
103
104 abstract protected function loadState() : array;
105
106 abstract protected function saveState(array $data) :
void;
107
108 abstract public function publishInfo(array $data) :
void;
109 }
110
```

File - /project/app/Utils/Validation/Exception/InvalidColumnCategory.php

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Validation\Exception;
4
5 use Exception;
6
7 class InvalidColumnCategory extends Exception
8 {
9
10 }
11
```

File - /project/app/Utils/Validation/Exception/MissingConfigParameter.php

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Validation\Exception;
4
5 use Exception;
6
7 class MissingConfigParameter extends Exception
8 {
9
10 }
11
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Aggregation;
4
5 use App\Repositories\AggregatedDataRepository;
6 use App\Utils\Aggregation\Exception\MissingAggregatorClass
7 use Carbon\Carbon;
8
9 class Aggregator
10 {
11     private $projectId;
12     private $fileId;
13     private $columnConfig;
14
15     private $aggregatedData = [];
16
17     private $aggregatedDataRepository;
18
19     private $dateColumnIndex = null;
20
21     private $data = [];
22
23     public function __construct(int $projectId, int
24 $fileId, array $columnConfig)
25     {
26         $this->aggregatedDataRepository = new
27 AggregatedDataRepository();
28         $this->projectId = $projectId;
29         $this->fileId = $fileId;
30         $this->columnConfig = $columnConfig;
31
32         foreach ($this->columnConfig as $columnId =>
33 $columnCfg) {
34             if ($columnCfg->machine_name === '
35 timestamp_date') {
36                 $this->dateColumnIndex = $columnId;
37             }
38         }
39     }
40
41     public function loadData($data)
42     {
43         $this->data = $data;
44     }
45
46     public function run()
```

```
43     {
44         foreach ($this->data as $row) {
45             $this->aggregateRow($row);
46         }
47         $this->store();
48     }
49     public function aggregateRow(array $row)
50     {
51         foreach ($row as $columnId => $columnVal) {
52             $date = $row[$this->dateColumnIndex] ?? null;
53             $year = null;
54
55             if (!empty($date)) {
56                 $year = (new Carbon($date))->year;
57             }
58
59             $aggregatorClass = $this->columnConfig[
60 $columnId]->aggregator;
61             if (!empty($aggregatorClass)) {
62                 $class = __NAMESPACE__ . "\\Aggregator\\"
63 . $aggregatorClass;
64                 if (!class_exists($class)) {
65                     throw new MissingAggregatorClass('The
66 aggregator class is missing.');
```

```
82 aggregatedDataRepository->increaseCount([
83     'project_id' => $this->projectId,
84     'file_id' => $this->fileId,
85     'year' => $year,
86     'machine_name' => $machine,
87     'value' => $value,
88     ], $data['count'], $data['
    aggregated_value'] ?? false) && $success;
89     }
90     }
91     }
92
93     return $success;
94 }
95 }
96 }
```

File - /project/app/Utils/Aggregation/Exception/MissingAggregatorClass.php

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Aggregation\Exception;
4
5 use Exception;
6
7 class MissingAggregatorClass extends Exception
8 {
9
10 }
11
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Aggregation\Aggregator;
4
5 class NullAggregator implements AggregatorInterface
6 {
7
8     public static function aggregate(
9         $year,
10        $machineName,
11        $value,
12        &$aggregatedData
13    ) {
14        return;
15    }
16 }
17
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Aggregation\Aggregator;
4
5 class SimpleAggregator implements AggregatorInterface
6 {
7     public static function aggregate($year, $machineName,
8     $value, &$aggregatedData)
9     {
10         if (!isset($aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][
11     $value]['count'])) {
12             $aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][$value]['
13     count'] = 0;
14         }
15     }
16 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Aggregation\Aggregator;
4
5 class DeceaseAggregator implements AggregatorInterface
6 {
7     public static function aggregate($year, $machineName,
8     $value, &$aggregatedData)
9     {
10         if (empty($value)) {
11             return;
12         }
13         $value = 'decease';
14
15         if (!isset($aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][
16     $value]['count'])) {
17             $aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][$value]['
18     count'] = 0;
19         }
20         $aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][$value]['
21     count']++;
22     }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Aggregation\Aggregator;
4
5 class AgeGroupAggregator implements AggregatorInterface
6 {
7     private static $ageGroups = [
8         [0, 19],
9         [20, 29],
10        [30, 39],
11        [40, 49],
12        [50, 59],
13        [60, 69],
14        [70, 79],
15        [80, 89],
16        [90, 99],
17        [100]
18    ];
19
20    public static function aggregate($year, $machineName,
21    $value, &$aggregatedData)
22    {
23        foreach (self::$ageGroups as $ageGroup) {
24            $ageGroupVal = implode('-', $ageGroup);
25
26            if (!isset($aggregatedData[$year][$machineName]
27            [[$ageGroupVal]['count']])) {
28                $aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][
29                $ageGroupVal]['count'] = 0;
30            }
31
32            if ($ageGroup[0] <= $value && $value <= (
33            $ageGroup[1] ?? 1000)) {
34                $aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][
35                $ageGroupVal]['count']++;
36            }
37        }
38    }
39 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Aggregation\Aggregator;
4
5 interface AggregatorInterface
6 {
7     public static function aggregate($year, $machineName,
8     $value, &$aggregatedData);
9 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Utils\Aggregation\Aggregator;
4
5 class SplitValueAggregator implements AggregatorInterface
6 {
7     public static function aggregate($year, $machineName,
8     $value, &$aggregatedData)
9     {
10         for ($i = 1; $i <= strlen($value); $i++) {
11             $valuePiece = substr($value, 0, $i);
12             if (!isset($aggregatedData[$year][$machineName]
13             [[$valuePiece]['count']])) {
14                 $aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][
15                 $valuePiece]['count'] = 0;
16             }
17             $aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][
18             $valuePiece]['count']++;
19             if ($i < strlen($value)) {
20                 $aggregatedData[$year][$machineName][
21                 $valuePiece]['aggregated_value'] = true;
22             }
23         }
24     }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Events;
4
5 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel;
6 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
7 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\PrivateChannel;
8 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\PresenceChannel;
9 use Illuminate\Foundation\Events\Dispatchable;
10 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\InteractsWithSockets;
11 use Illuminate\Contracts\Broadcasting\ShouldBroadcast;
12 use Illuminate\Contracts\Broadcasting\ShouldBroadcastNow;
13
14 class WsTestEvent implements ShouldBroadcastNow
15 {
16     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithSockets,
17     SerializesModels;
18
19     public $message = '';
20
21     /**
22      * Create a new event instance.
23      *
24      * @return void
25      */
26     public function __construct($message)
27     {
28         $this->message = $message;
29     }
30
31     /**
32      * Get the channels the event should broadcast on.
33      *
34      * @return \Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel|array
35      */
36     public function broadcastOn()
37     {
38         return ['ws-user_1'];
39         //return new PrivateChannel('test-channel-p.1');
40     }
41 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Events;
4
5 use App\Models\Project;
6 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel;
7 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
8 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\PrivateChannel;
9 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\PresenceChannel;
10 use Illuminate\Foundation\Events\Dispatchable;
11 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\InteractsWithSockets;
12 use Illuminate\Contracts\Broadcasting\ShouldBroadcast;
13
14 class ProjectDeleted
15 {
16     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithSockets,
17     SerializesModels;
18
19     /**
20      * @var Project
21      */
22     public $project;
23
24     /**
25      * Create a new event instance.
26      *
27      * @return void
28      */
29     public function __construct(Project $project)
30     {
31         $this->project = $project;
32     }
33
34     /**
35      * Get the channels the event should broadcast on.
36      *
37      * @return \Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel|array
38      */
39     public function broadcastOn()
40     {
41         return new PrivateChannel('channel-name');
42     }
43 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Events;
4
5 use App\Models\Project;
6 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel;
7 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
8 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\PrivateChannel;
9 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\PresenceChannel;
10 use Illuminate\Foundation\Events\Dispatchable;
11 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\InteractsWithSockets;
12 use Illuminate\Contracts\Broadcasting\ShouldBroadcast;
13
14 class ProjectUpdated
15 {
16     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithSockets,
17     SerializesModels;
18
19     /**
20      * @var Project
21      */
22     public $project;
23
24     /**
25      * Create a new event instance.
26      *
27      * @return void
28      */
29     public function __construct(Project $project)
30     {
31         $this->project = $project;
32     }
33
34     /**
35      * Get the channels the event should broadcast on.
36      *
37      * @return \Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel|array
38      */
39     public function broadcastOn()
40     {
41         return new PrivateChannel('channel-name');
42     }
43 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Events;
4
5 use App\User;
6 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel;
7 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\PrivateChannel;
8
9 class UserRegistered extends AbstractEntityEvent
10 {
11     public $user;
12
13     /**
14      * Create a new event instance.
15      *
16      * @param User $user
17      */
18     public function __construct(User $user)
19     {
20         $this->user = $user;
21     }
22 }
23
```

File - /project/app/Events/AbstractEntityEvent.php

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Events;
4
5 use Illuminate\Broadcasting\InteractsWithSockets;
6 use Illuminate\Foundation\Events\Dispatchable;
7 use Illuminate\Queue\SerializesModels;
8
9 abstract class AbstractEntityEvent
10 {
11     use Dispatchable, InteractsWithSockets,
12     SerializesModels;
13 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Auth;
7
8 class File extends Model
9 {
10     protected $fillable = [
11         'type',
12         'project_id',
13         'path',
14         'file_name',
15         'mime_type',
16         'size',
17         'preview',
18     ];
19
20     protected $casts = [
21         'preview' => 'array',
22     ];
23
24     protected $dates = [
25         'created_at',
26         'updated_at',
27     ];
28
29     public static function boot()
30     {
31         parent::boot();
32         static::creating(function ($model) {
33             $user = Auth::user();
34             if (!$user) {
35                 return;
36             }
37
38             $model->user_id = $user->id;
39         });
40     }
41
42     public function columnDefinitions()
43     {
44         return $this->hasMany(ColumnDefinition::class)->
45         orderBy('column_number', 'asc');
46     }
47 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class Option extends Model
8 {
9     public $timestamps = false;
10
11     protected $fillable = [
12         'key',
13         'value',
14     ];
15
16     protected $casts = [
17         'value',
18     ];
19 }
20
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class AtcData extends Model
8 {
9     protected $fillable = [
10         'project_id',
11         'code',
12         'name',
13     ];
14
15     public $timestamps = false;
16 }
17
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class BnoData extends Model
8 {
9     protected $fillable = [
10         'project_id',
11         'code',
12         'name',
13     ];
14
15     public $timestamps = false;
16 }
17
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class Project extends Model
8 {
9     protected $fillable = [
10         'name',
11         'archived',
12         'upload_done',
13     ];
14
15     public function aggregatedData()
16     {
17         return $this->hasMany('App\Models\AggregatedData'
18 , 'project_id', 'id');
19     }
20 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class OenoData extends Model
8 {
9     protected $fillable = [
10         'project_id',
11         'code',
12         'name',
13     ];
14
15     public $timestamps = false;
16 }
17
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class SamiConfig extends Model
8 {
9     public $timestamps = true;
10
11     protected $fillable = [
12         'project_id',
13         'factors',
14         'type',
15         'name',
16         'starting_date',
17         'ending_date',
18         'category',
19         'code',
20         'relative_range_start',
21         'relative_range_end',
22         'frequency',
23     ];
24
25     protected $casts = [
26         'factors' => 'array',
27     ];
28
29     protected $dates = [
30         'created_at',
31         'updated_at',
32         'starting_date',
33         'ending_date',
34     ];
35
36     public function samiConfigMilestone()
37     {
38         return $this->hasMany('App\Models\
39         SamiConfigMilestone', 'sami_config_id', 'id');
40     }
41 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class AggregatedData extends Model
8 {
9     public $timestamps = true;
10
11     protected $fillable = [
12         'project_id',
13         'file_id',
14         'year',
15         'machine_name',
16         'value',
17         'count',
18         'aggregated_value',
19     ];
20
21     public function user()
22     {
23         return $this->belongsTo('App\Models\Project', '
project_id', 'id');
24     }
25 }
26
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Baum\Node;
6
7 class ColumnCategory extends Node
8 {
9     protected $fillable = [
10         'parent_id',
11         'lft',
12         'rgt',
13         'depth',
14         'name',
15         'machine_name',
16         'validators',
17     ];
18
19     protected $dates = [
20         'created_at',
21         'updated_at',
22     ];
23
24     protected $casts = [
25         'validators' => 'array',
26         'logical_conditions' => 'array',
27     ];
28 }
29
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class ColumnDefinition extends Model
8 {
9     protected $fillable = [
10         'column_number',
11         'column_name',
12         'category',
13         'project_id',
14         'file_id',
15     ];
16
17     protected $dates = [
18         'created_at',
19         'updated_at',
20     ];
21     public function file()
22     {
23         return $this->belongsTo(File::class);
24     }
25 }
26
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Models;
4
5 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
6
7 class SamiConfigMilestone extends Model
8 {
9     public $timestamps = true;
10
11     protected $fillable = [
12         'sami_config_id',
13         'milestone_category',
14         'milestone_code',
15         'milestone_relative_range_start',
16         'milestone_relative_range_end',
17         'milestone_frequency',
18     ];
19
20     public function samiConfig()
21     {
22         return $this->belongsTo('App\Models\SamiConfig', '
sami_config_id', 'id');
23     }
24 }
25
```

```
1 <?php
2 /**
3  * Created by PhpStorm.
4  * User: frankj
5  * Date: 5/4/17
6  * Time: 7:14 PM
7  */
8
9 namespace App\Traits;
10
11 use Exception;
12 use Illuminate\Auth\AuthenticatonException;
13 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\ModelNotFoundException;
14 use Illuminate\Validation\ValidationException;
15 use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response as
    HttpFoundationResponse;
16 use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Exception\HttpException;
17
18 trait ApiExceptionHandlerTrait
19 {
20     /**
21      * Response status code
22      *
23      * @var int
24      */
25     protected $statusCode = HttpFoundationResponse::
    HTTP_OK;
26
27     /**
28      * Response errors
29      *
30      * @var array
31      */
32     protected $errors = [];
33
34     /**
35      * Sets the statusCode for the response
36      *
37      * @param $statusCode
38      * @return $this
39      */
40     public function setStatusCode($statusCode)
41     {
42         $this->statusCode = $statusCode;
43
44         return $this;
45     }

```

```
46
47     /**
48      * Returns the current statusCode
49      *
50      * @return int
51      */
52     public function getStatusCode()
53     {
54         return $this->statusCode;
55     }
56
57     /**
58      * Creates a new JSON response based on exception type
59      *
60      * @param Exception $exception
61      * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
62      */
63     protected function getJsonResponseForException(
64     Exception $exception)
65     {
66         switch (true) {
67             case $this->isValidationException($exception):
68                 return $response = $this->
69                 respondFailedValidation($exception);
70             case $this->isModelNotFoundException(
71             $exception):
72                 return $response = $this->respondNotFound
73                 ();
74             case $this->isHttpException($exception):
75                 return $response = $this->
76                 respondWithHttpException($exception);
77             case $this->isAuthenticationException(
78             $exception):
79                 return $response = $this->
80                 respondWithAuthenticationException($exception);
81             default:
82                 return $response = $this->
83                 respondBadRequest($exception);
84         }
85     }
86
87     /**
88      * Returns a json response for HttpException.
89      *
90      * @param Exception $exception
91      * @return mixed
```

```
84     */
85     public function respondWithHttpException($exception)
86     {
87         return $this->setStatusCode($exception->
getStatusCode())
88             ->withError($exception->getMessage())
89             ->respond();
90     }
91
92     /**
93      * Returns a json response for HttpException.
94      *
95      * @param Exception $exception
96      * @return mixed
97      */
98     public function respondWithAuthenticationException(
$exception)
99     {
100         return $this->setStatusCode(
HttpExceptionResponse::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED)
101             ->withError($exception->getMessage())
102             ->respond();
103     }
104
105     /**
106      * Returns a json response for
UnsupportedJsonRequestException.
107      *
108      * @param Exception $exception
109      * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
110      */
111     public function responseUnsupportedJsonRequest(
$exception)
112     {
113         return $this->setStatusCode(
HttpExceptionResponse::HTTP_FORBIDDEN)
114             ->withValidationErrors($exception)
115             ->respond();
116     }
117
118     /**
119      * Returns a jsons error response with validation
errors
120      *
121      * @param ValidationException $exception
122      * @return mixed
123      */
```

```
124     public function respondFailedValidation($exception)
125     {
126         return $this->setStatusCode(
    HttpFoundationResponse::HTTP_UNPROCESSABLE_ENTITY)
127             ->withValidationErrors($exception)
128             ->respond();
129     }
130
131     /**
132      * Returns a json response for generic bad request.
133      *
134      * @param Exception $exception
135      * @param string $message
136      * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
137      */
138     protected function respondBadRequest($exception,
    $message = 'Bad request')
139     {
140         if (env('APP_DEBUG') === true) {
141             return $this->setStatusCode(
    HttpFoundationResponse::HTTP_BAD_REQUEST)
142                 ->withError($exception->getMessage())
143                 ->respond();
144         }
145
146         return $this->setStatusCode(
    HttpFoundationResponse::HTTP_BAD_REQUEST)
147             ->withError($message)
148             ->respond();
149     }
150
151     /**
152      * Returns json response for model not found.
153      *
154      * @param string $message
155      * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
156      */
157     protected function respondNotFound($message = 'Not
    found')
158     {
159         return $this->setStatusCode(
    HttpFoundationResponse::HTTP_NOT_FOUND)
160             ->withError($message)
161             ->respond();
162     }
163
164     /**
```

```
165     * Returns json response.
166     *
167     * @return \Illuminate\Http\JsonResponse
168     */
169     protected function respond()
170     {
171         $payload['errors'] = $this->errors ?: [];
172
173         return response()->json($payload, $this->
getStatusCode());
174     }
175
176     /**
177     * Determines if the given exception is an Eloquent
model not found.
178     *
179     * @param Exception $exception
180     * @return bool
181     */
182     protected function isModelNotFoundException(Exception
$exception)
183     {
184         return $exception instanceof
ModelNotFoundHttpException;
185     }
186
187     /**
188     * Determines if the given exception is a
ValidationException.
189     *
190     * @param Exception $exception
191     * @return bool
192     */
193     protected function isValidException(Exception
$exception)
194     {
195         return $exception instanceof ValidationException;
196     }
197
198     /**
199     * Determines if the given exception is a
HttpException.
200     *
201     * @param Exception $exception
202     * @return bool
203     */
204     protected function isHttpException(Exception
```

```
204 $exception)
205     {
206         return $exception instanceof HttpException;
207     }
208
209     /**
210      * Determines if the given exception is a
211      * HttpException.
212      * @param Exception $exception
213      * @return bool
214      */
215     protected function isAuthenticatedException(
216     Exception $exception)
217     {
218         return $exception instanceof
219     AuthenticationException;
220     }
221
222     /**
223      * Returns a single error response entry
224      * @param string $title
225      * @param string $detail
226      * @param array $source
227      * @return mixed
228      */
229     protected function getErrorResponseEntry($title,
230     $detail = "", $source = [])
231     {
232         if (!$source) {
233             $source = ["pointer" => ''];
234         }
235
236         return [
237             'status' => (string)$this->getStatusCode(),
238             'source' => $source,
239             'title' => $title,
240             'detail' => $detail,
241         ];
242     }
243
244     /**
245      * Extracts the validation errors provided by the
246      * ValidationException
247      * @param Exception
```

```
246     * @return array
247     */
248     protected function extractValidationErrors($exception
    )
249     {
250         $responseData = [];
251
252         $validationErrors = json_decode($exception->
validator->getMessageBag());
253
254         foreach ($validationErrors as $fieldName =>
$errorData) {
255             $responseData = array_merge($responseData,
$this->extractErrorMessage($fieldName, $errorData));
256         }
257         return $responseData;
258     }
259
260     /**
261     * Extracts the error messages for a single
validation error
262     *
263     * @param $fieldName
264     * @param $errorData
265     * @return array
266     */
267     protected function extractErrorMessage($fieldName,
$errorData)
268     {
269         $extractErrorMessages = [];
270
271         if (is_array($errorData)) {
272             foreach ($errorData as $error) {
273                 $extractErrorMessages[] = $this->
getErrorResponseEntry(
274                     'Invalid parameter',
275                     $error,
276                     ["pointer" => "/data/attributes/{
$fieldName}"]
277                 );
278             }
279
280             return $extractErrorMessages;
281         }
282
283         $extractErrorMessages[] = $this->
getErrorResponseEntry(
```

```
284         'Invalid parameter',
285         $errorData,
286         ["pointer" => "/data/attributes/{fieldName}"]
    ]
287     );
288     return $extractErrorMessages;
289 }
290
291 /**
292  * Adds an error to the response errors
293  *
294  * @param $message
295  * @return $this
296  */
297 protected function withError($message)
298 {
299     $this->errors[] = $this->getErrorResponseEntry(
300     $message);
301     return $this;
302 }
303
304 /**
305  * Adds the validation errors provided by the
306  * ValidationException to the response errors
307  *
308  * @param $exception
309  * @return $this
310  */
311 protected function withValidationErrors($exception)
312 {
313     $this->errors = array_merge($this->errors, $this
314     ->extractValidationErrors($exception));
315     return $this;
316 }
317 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Console;
4
5 use Illuminate\Console\Scheduling\Schedule;
6 use Illuminate\Foundation\Console\Kernel as ConsoleKernel;
7 use SensioLabs\Security\Command\SecurityCheckerCommand;
8 use SensioLabs\Security\SecurityChecker;
9
10 class Kernel extends ConsoleKernel
11 {
12     /**
13      * The Artisan commands provided by your application.
14      *
15      * @var array
16      */
17     protected $commands = [
18         //
19     ];
20
21     /**
22      * Define the application's command schedule.
23      *
24      * @param \Illuminate\Console\Scheduling\Schedule
25      * $schedule
26      * @return void
27      * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD.UnusedFormalParameter)
28      */
29     protected function schedule(Schedule $schedule)
30     {
31         // $schedule->command('inspire')
32         //             ->hourly();
33     }
34
35     /**
36      * Register the commands for the application.
37      *
38      * @return void
39      */
40     protected function commands()
41     {
42         $this->load(__DIR__.'/Commands');
43
44         if (class_exists(SecurityCheckerCommand::class)) {
45             $this->registerCommand(new SecurityCheckerCommand(new SecurityChecker()));
46         }
47     }
48 }
```

File - /project/app/Console/Kernel.php

```
46     }
47
48     require base_path('routes/console.php');
49 }
50 }
51
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Console\Commands;
4
5 use Illuminate\Console\Command;
6 use App\Events\WsTestEvent;
7 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Redis;
8 use Carbon\Carbon;
9
10 class WsTest extends Command
11 {
12     /**
13      * The name and signature of the console command.
14      *
15      * @var string
16      */
17     protected $signature = 'ws:test';
18
19     /**
20      * The console command description.
21      *
22      * @var string
23      */
24     protected $description = 'Command description';
25
26     /**
27      * Create a new command instance.
28      *
29      * @return void
30      */
31     public function __construct()
32     {
33         parent::__construct();
34     }
35
36     /**
37      * Execute the console command.
38      *
39      * @return mixed
40      */
41     public function handle()
42     {
43         for ($i = 1; $i <= 150; $i++) {
44             Redis::publish('ws-user_1', json_encode([
45                 'event' => 'test-event',
46                 'data' => 'Data ' . $i . ' - ' . Carbon::
47 now())
```

File - /project/app/Console/Commands/WsTest.php

```
47         ]));
48     }
49
50     //event(new WsTestEvent('Test Message ' . Carbon::
now()));
51 }
52 }
53
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Listeners;
4
5 use App\Events\UserRegistered;
6 use App\Mail\Mailers\UserMailer;
7
8 class UserRegisterListener
9 {
10     /**
11      * @var \App\Mail\Mailers\UserMailer
12      */
13     private $mailer;
14
15     /**
16      * UserRegisterListener constructor.
17      *
18      * @param \App\Mail\Mailers\UserMailer $mailer
19      */
20     public function __construct(UserMailer $mailer)
21     {
22         $this->mailer = $mailer;
23     }
24
25     /**
26      * Handle the event.
27      *
28      * @param UserRegistered $event
29      * @return void
30      */
31     public function handle(UserRegistered $event)
32     {
33         $this->mailer->sendEmailConfirmationTo($event->
34         user)->send();
35     }
36 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Listeners;
4
5 use App\Events\ProjectDeleted;
6 use App\Repositories\FileRepository;
7 use Illuminate\Queue\InteractsWithQueue;
8 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
9
10 class ManageProjectFilesOnDeleteListener
11 {
12     /**
13      * @var FileRepository
14      */
15     private $fileRepository;
16
17     /**
18      * Create the event listener.
19      *
20      * @return void
21      */
22     public function __construct(FileRepository
23 $fileRepository)
24     {
25         $this->fileRepository = $fileRepository;
26     }
27
28     /**
29      * Handle the event.
30      *
31      * @param object $event
32      * @return void
33      */
34     public function handle(ProjectDeleted $event)
35     {
36         $projectId = $event->project->id;
37         $this->fileRepository->deleteFileByProjectId(
38 $projectId);
39     }
40 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Listeners;
4
5 use App\Events\ProjectUpdated;
6 use App\Repositories\FileRepository;
7 use Illuminate\Queue\InteractsWithQueue;
8 use Illuminate\Contracts\Queue\ShouldQueue;
9
10 class ManageProjectFilesOnUpdateListener
11 {
12     /**
13      * @var FileRepository
14      */
15     private $fileRepository;
16
17     /**
18      * Create the event listener.
19      *
20      * @return void
21      */
22     public function __construct(FileRepository
23 $fileRepository)
24     {
25         $this->fileRepository = $fileRepository;
26     }
27
28     /**
29      * Handle the event.
30      *
31      * @param object $event
32      * @return void
33      */
34     public function handle(ProjectUpdated $event)
35     {
36         if ((int)$event->project->archived === 1) {
37             $projectId = $event->project->id;
38             $this->fileRepository->deleteFileByProjectId(
39 $projectId);
40         }
41     }
42 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Providers;
4
5 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\DB;
6 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Schema;
7 use Illuminate\Support\ServiceProvider;
8
9 class AppServiceProvider extends ServiceProvider
10 {
11     /**
12      * Bootstrap any application services.
13      *
14      * @return void
15      */
16     public function boot()
17     {
18         // Fix MariaDB utf8mb4 bug.
19         if (DB::getDefaultConnection() === 'mysql') {
20             Schema::defaultStringLength(191);
21         }
22     }
23
24     /**
25      * Register any application services.
26      *
27      * @return void
28      */
29     public function register()
30     {
31         //
32     }
33 }
34
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Providers;
4
5 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Gate;
6 use Illuminate\Foundation\Support\Providers\
  AuthServiceProvider as ServiceProvider;
7
8 class AuthServiceProvider extends ServiceProvider
9 {
10     /**
11      * The policy mappings for the application.
12      *
13      * @var array
14      */
15     protected $policies = [
16         'App\Model' => 'App\Policies\ModelPolicy',
17     ];
18
19     /**
20      * Register any authentication / authorization
  services.
21      *
22      * @return void
23      */
24     public function boot()
25     {
26         $this->registerPolicies();
27
28         //
29     }
30 }
31
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Providers;
4
5 use App\Events\ProjectDeleted;
6 use App\Events\ProjectUpdated;
7 use App\Events\UserRegistered;
8 use App\Listeners\ManageProjectFilesOnDeleteListener;
9 use App\Listeners\ManageProjectFilesOnUpdateListener;
10 use App\Listeners\UserRegisterListener;
11 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Event;
12 use Illuminate\Auth\Events\Registered;
13 use Illuminate\Auth\Listeners\
    SendEmailVerificationNotification;
14 use Illuminate\Foundation\Support\Providers\
    EventServiceProvider as ServiceProvider;
15
16 class EventServiceProvider extends ServiceProvider
17 {
18     /**
19      * The event listener mappings for the application.
20      *
21      * @var array
22      */
23     protected $listen = [
24         UserRegistered::class => [
25             UserRegisterListener::class,
26         ],
27         ProjectUpdated::class => [
28             ManageProjectFilesOnUpdateListener::class,
29         ],
30         ProjectDeleted::class => [
31             ManageProjectFilesOnDeleteListener::class,
32         ],
33     ];
34
35     /**
36      * Register any events for your application.
37      *
38      * @return void
39      */
40     public function boot()
41     {
42         parent::boot();
43
44         //
45     }
```

File - /project/app/Providers/EventServiceProvider.php

46 }

47

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Providers;
4
5 use App\Repositories\FileRepository;
6 use Illuminate\Http\Response;
7 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Route;
8 use Illuminate\Foundation\Support\Providers\
  RouteServiceProvider as ServiceProvider;
9
10 class RouteServiceProvider extends ServiceProvider
11 {
12     /**
13      * This namespace is applied to your controller routes
14      *
15      * In addition, it is set as the URL generator's root
  namespace.
16      *
17      * @var string
18      */
19     protected $namespace = 'App\Http\Controllers';
20
21     /**
22      * Define your route model bindings, pattern filters,
  etc.
23      *
24      * @return void
25      */
26     public function boot()
27     {
28         parent::boot();
29         Route::bind('filetype', function ($fileType) {
30             if (!in_array($fileType, FileRepository::
  allowedTypes())) {
31                 abort(Response::HTTP_BAD_REQUEST, 'The
  type parameter is invalid.');
```

File - /project/app/Providers/RouteServiceProvider.php

```
42     public function map()
43     {
44         $this->mapApiRoutes();
45
46         $this->mapWebRoutes();
47
48         //
49     }
50
51     /**
52      * Define the "web" routes for the application.
53      *
54      * These routes all receive session state, CSRF
55      * protection, etc.
56      *
57      * @return void
58      */
59     protected function mapWebRoutes()
60     {
61         Route::middleware('web')
62             ->namespace($this->namespace)
63             ->group(base_path('routes/web.php'));
64     }
65
66     /**
67      * Define the "api" routes for the application.
68      *
69      * These routes are typically stateless.
70      *
71      * @return void
72      */
73     protected function mapApiRoutes()
74     {
75         Route::prefix('api')
76             ->middleware('api')
77             ->namespace($this->namespace)
78             ->group(base_path('routes/api.php'));
79     }
80 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Providers;
4
5 use Illuminate\Support\ServiceProvider;
6 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Broadcast;
7
8 class BroadcastServiceProvider extends ServiceProvider
9 {
10     /**
11      * Bootstrap any application services.
12      *
13      * @return void
14      */
15     public function boot()
16     {
17         Broadcast::routes();
18
19         require base_path('routes/channels.php');
20     }
21 }
22
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Exceptions;
4
5 use App\Traits\ApiExceptionHandlerTrait;
6 use App\Traits\ApiTrait;
7 use Exception;
8 use Illuminate\Auth\AuthenticatingException;
9 use Illuminate\Foundation\Exceptions\Handler as
  ExceptionHandler;
10 use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;
11
12 class Handler extends ExceptionHandler
13 {
14     use ApiExceptionHandlerTrait;
15
16     /**
17      * A list of the exception types that should not be
18      * reported.
19      * @var array
20      */
21     protected $dontReport = [
22         \Illuminate\Auth\AuthenticatingException::class,
23         \Illuminate\Auth\Access\AuthorizationException::
24         class,
25         \Symfony\Component\HttpKernel\Exception\
26         HttpException::class,
27         \Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\
28         ModelNotFoundException::class,
29         \Illuminate\Session\TokenMismatchException::class,
30         \Illuminate\Validation\ValidationException::class,
31         \App\Exceptions\Api\PagerLimitException::class,
32     ];
33
34     /**
35      * Report or log an exception.
36      * This is a great spot to send exceptions to Sentry,
37      * Bugsnag, etc.
38      *
39      * @param \Exception $exception
40      * @return void
41      */
42     public function report(Exception $exception)
43     {
44         parent::report($exception);
45     }
46 }
```

```
42     }
43
44     /**
45      * Render an exception into an HTTP response.
46      *
47      * @param \Illuminate\Http\Request $request
48      * @param \Exception $exception
49      * @return mixed
50      */
51     public function render($request, Exception $exception)
52     {
53         if ($request->expectsJson()) {
54             return $this->getJsonResponseForException(
55                 $exception);
56         }
57         return parent::render($request, $exception);
58     }
59
60     /**
61      * Convert an authentication exception into an
62      * unauthenticated response.
63      *
64      * @param \Illuminate\Http\Request $request
65      * @param \Illuminate\Auth\AuthenticationException
66      * $exception
67      * @return mixed
68      *
69      * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD.UnusedFormalParameter)
70      */
71     protected function unauthenticated($request,
72         AuthenticationException $exception)
73     {
74         if ($request->expectsJson()) {
75             return response()->json(['error' => '
76                 Unauthenticated.'], 401);
77         }
78         if (!empty($request->route()) && $request->route
79             ()->getName() === 'profile') {
80             return response()->redirectToRoute('home');
81         }
82         abort(Response::HTTP_UNAUTHORIZED, '
83             Unauthenticated.');
```

```
1 <?php
2 /**
3  * Created by PhpStorm.
4  * User: kovacsg
5  * Date: 2017.06.09.
6  * Time: 11:59
7  */
8
9 namespace App\Exceptions\Api;
10
11 use \Exception;
12
13 class PagerLimitException extends Exception
14 {
15     public function __construct()
16     {
17         parent::__construct('Maximum pager limit exceeded
18         .', null, null);
19     }
20 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Jobs\ImportCodeTable;
6 use App\Models\File;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
8 use Illuminate\Http\UploadedFile;
9 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\Storage;
10
11 class FileRepository extends BaseRepository
12 {
13     public const CODE_DATA_TYPES = [
14         'bno',
15         'atc',
16         'oeno',
17     ];
18     public const DATA_TYPES = [
19         'data-demography',
20         'data-icd',
21         'data-atc',
22         'data-icpm',
23     ];
24
25     public const PRIMARY_TYPE = 'data-demography';
26
27     public static function allowedTypes()
28     {
29         return array_merge(self::CODE_DATA_TYPES, self::
  DATA_TYPES);
30     }
31
32     public function getModelClass()
33     {
34         return File::class;
35     }
36
37     public function saveFile(UploadedFile $file, string
  $type, int $projectId)
38     {
39         $preview = null;
40
41         $fileName = $this->createFilename($file);
42         $mime = str_replace('/', '-', $file->getMimeType
  ());
43         $dateFolder = date('Y-m-d');
```

```
44
45     $filePath = 'upload/' . $mime . '/' . $dateFolder
    . '/';
46     $finalPath = Storage::disk('local')->path(
    $filePath);
47     $fileSize = $file->getSize();
48     $file->move($finalPath, $fileName);
49
50     if (in_array($type, self::DATA_TYPES)) {
51         $preview = $this->createPreview($finalPath .
    $fileName);
52     }
53
54     $file = File::create([
55         'type' => $type,
56         'project_id' => $projectId,
57         'path' => $filePath,
58         'file_name' => $fileName,
59         'mime_type' => $mime,
60         'size' => $fileSize,
61         'preview' => $preview,
62     ]);
63
64     if (in_array($file->type, self::CODE_DATA_TYPES
    )) {
65         ImportCodeTable::dispatch($file->id)->onQueue(
    'default');
66     }
67
68     return $file;
69 }
70
71 public function getPrimaryFileByFile(File $file)
72 {
73     return $this->model->newQuery()
74         ->where('project_id', $file->project_id)
75         ->where('type', static::PRIMARY_TYPE)
76         ->first();
77 }
78
79 protected function createFilename(UploadedFile $file)
80 {
81     $extension = $file->getClientOriginalExtension();
82     $filename = $file->getBasename('.') . $extension;
83     $filename .= '_' . md5(time()) . '.' . $extension;
84
85     return $filename;
```

```
86     }
87
88     protected function createPreview(string $path)
89     {
90         $handle = fopen($path, 'r');
91
92         // Get header data from the first line.
93         $headers = fgetcsv($handle, 0, config('app.
csv_separator'));
94         if (!$headers) {
95             return [];
96         }
97
98         $columnCount = count($headers);
99         $columns = [];
100
101         $i = 0;
102         while (!feof($handle) && $i < 7) {
103             $data = fgetcsv($handle, 0, config('app.
csv_separator'));
104
105             if (!$data || count($data) < $columnCount) {
106                 continue;
107             }
108
109             for ($j = 0; $j < $columnCount; $j++) {
110                 $columns[$j][$i] = $data[$j];
111             }
112
113             $i++;
114         }
115
116         fclose($handle);
117
118         return [
119             'headers' => $headers,
120             'data' => $columns,
121         ];
122     }
123
124     public function deleteFileById(int $id)
125     {
126         $file = $this->getById($id);
127
128         $this->deleteFile($file);
129     }
130
```

File - /project/app/Repositories/FileRepository.php

```
131     public function deleteFileByProjectId(int $id)
132     {
133         $files = $this->model->where('project_id', '=',
134         $id)->get();
135         foreach ($files as $file) {
136             $this->deleteFile($file);
137         }
138     }
139
140     private function deleteFile(File $file)
141     {
142         if (Storage::disk('local')->exists($file->path .
143         $file->file_name)) {
144             Storage::disk('local')->delete($file->path .
145             $file->file_name);
146             (new AggregatedDataRepository())->deleteByFileId(
147             $file->id);
148             $file->delete();
149         }
150     }
151 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\User;
6 use Carbon\Carbon;
7 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Builder;
8 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
9
10 class UserRepository extends BaseRepository
11 {
12     protected $allowedOrders = [
13         'id',
14         'created_at',
15         'updated_at',
16         'id',
17         'email',
18         'name',
19     ];
20     protected $allowedFilters = [
21         'email',
22         'name',
23         'status',
24     ];
25
26     public function getModelClass()
27     {
28         return User::class;
29     }
30
31     public function isUserActive(String $email)
32     {
33         /**
34          * @var Builder $query
35          */
36         $query = $this->model
37             ->where('email', $email)
38             ->whereNotNull('email_verified_at');
39         $activeUsersWithEmail = $query->count();
40
41         return $activeUsersWithEmail === 1;
42     }
43
44     public function createUser($data)
45     {
46         $data['password'] = self::hash($data['password']);
```

```
47
48     /**
49      * @var User $user
50      */
51     $user = $this->store($data);
52     if (isset($data['roles'])) {
53         $user->syncRoles($data['roles']);
54     }
55     return $user;
56 }
57
58 public function updateUser($id, $data)
59 {
60     if (isset($data['password'])) {
61         $data['password'] = self::hash($data['password
62     ]]);
63 }
64
65     /**
66      * @var User $user
67      */
68     $user = $this->update($id, $data);
69     if (isset($data['roles'])) {
70         $user->syncRoles($data['roles']);
71     }
72     return $user;
73 }
74
75 public static function hash($value)
76 {
77     return \Hash::make($value);
78 }
79
80 public function getUserByEmail(String $email)
81 {
82     return $this->model->where('email', $email)->first
83     ();
84 }
85
86 public function getModel()
87 {
88     return $this->model;
89 }
90
91 protected function filterQuery($filterName,
92 $filterValue, $query)
93 {
```

```
91     switch ($filterName) {
92         case 'email':
93             return $query->where('email', 'LIKE', '%'
. $filterValue . '%');
94         case 'name':
95             return $query->where('name', 'LIKE', '%'
. $filterValue . '%');
96         default:
97             return $query;
98     }
99 }
100 public function delete($id)
101 {
102     /** @var User $user */
103     $user = $this->model->findOrFail($id);
104     return $user->delete();
105 }
106
107 public function verifyEmail($token)
108 {
109     $user = $this->model->where('verification_token'
, '=', $token)->first();
110
111     if (!empty($user)) {
112         $user->verification_token = null;
113         $user->email_verified_at = Carbon::now();
114         $user->save();
115         return true;
116     }
117     return false;
118 }
119 }
120
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\AtcData;
6 use App\Repositories\Traits\GetByCode;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
8
9 class AtcDataRepository extends BaseRepository
10 {
11     use GetByCode;
12
13     public function getModelClass()
14     {
15         return AtcData::class;
16     }
17 }
18
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\BnoData;
6 use App\Repositories\Traits\GetByCode;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
8
9 class BnoDataRepository extends BaseRepository
10 {
11     use GetByCode;
12
13     public function getModelClass()
14     {
15         return BnoData::class;
16     }
17 }
18
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\Project;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
7
8 class ProjectRepository extends BaseRepository
9 {
10     protected $allowedFilters = [
11         'name',
12         'archived',
13         'upload_done',
14     ];
15     protected $allowedOrders = [
16         'id',
17         'created_at',
18         'updated_at',
19         'name',
20         'archived',
21         'upload_done',
22     ];
23
24     public function store($data)
25     {
26         $data['name'] = !empty($data['name']) ? $data['
name'] : '';
27         $data['archived'] = 0;
28         $data['upload_done'] = 0;
29         return parent::store($data);
30     }
31
32     protected function filterQuery($filterName,
$filterValue, $query)
33     {
34         switch ($filterName) {
35             case 'name':
36                 return $query->where('name', 'LIKE', '%'.
$filterValue . '%');
37             case 'archived':
38                 if (abs($filterValue)) {
39                     return $query->where('archived',
$filterValue == 1 ? true : false);
40                 }
41                 return $query;
42             case 'upload_done':
```

File - /project/app/Repositories/ProjectRepository.php

```
43         if (abs($filterValue)) {
44             return $query->where('upload_done',
$filterValue == 1 ? true : false);
45         }
46         return $query;
47     default:
48         return $query;
49     }
50 }
51
52     public function getAllByAttribute($attribute, $data,
$operator = '=')
53     {
54         return $this->model->where($attribute, $operator,
$data)->get();
55     }
56
57     public function getModelClass()
58     {
59         return Project::class;
60     }
61 }
62
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\OenoData;
6 use App\Repositories\Traits\GetByCode;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
8
9 class OenoDataRepository extends BaseRepository
10 {
11     use GetByCode;
12
13     public function getModelClass()
14     {
15         return OenoData::class;
16     }
17 }
18
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\SamiConfig;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
7
8 class SamiConfigRepository extends BaseRepository
9 {
10     protected $allowedFilters = [
11         'project_id',
12         'type',
13     ];
14
15     protected $allowedOrders = [
16         'id',
17         'created_at',
18         'updated_at',
19         'project_id',
20     ];
21
22     const TYPES = [
23         'segmentation',
24         'progression',
25         'prediction',
26     ];
27
28     const CATEGORY_ICD = 'ICD';
29     const CATEGORY_ICPM = 'ICPM';
30     const CATEGORY_ATC = 'ATC';
31     const CATEGORY_DEATH = 'Death';
32
33     const CATEGORIES = [
34         self::CATEGORY_ICD,
35         self::CATEGORY_ICPM,
36         self::CATEGORY_ATC,
37         self::CATEGORY_DEATH,
38     ];
39
40     private $chartResult = [
41         'segmentation',
42     ];
43
44     private $gridResult = [
45         'progression',
46         'prediction',
```

```
47     ];
48
49     protected function filterQuery($filterName,
50     $filterValue, $query)
51     {
52         switch ($filterName) {
53             case 'project_id':
54             case 'type':
55                 return $query->where($filterName,
56     $filterValue);
57             default:
58                 return $query;
59         }
60     }
61
62     public function getModelClass()
63     {
64         return SamiConfig::class;
65     }
66
67     public function getChartResult($type)
68     {
69         if (!in_array($type, $this->chartResult)) {
70             return [];
71         }
72
73         $lineChart = [
74             ["x" => 1, "y" => 10,],
75             ["x" => 2, "y" => 13,],
76             ["x" => 3, "y" => 15,],
77             ["x" => 4, "y" => 20,],
78             ["x" => 5, "y" => 55,],
79             ["x" => 6, "y" => 40,],
80             ["x" => 7, "y" => 43,],
81             ["x" => 8, "y" => 22,],
82             ["x" => 9, "y" => 10,],
83             ["x" => 10, "y" => 2,],
84         ];
85
86         $clusterCharts = [];
87         for ($i = 1; $i <= 12; $i++) {
88             $clusterCharts[] = ["title" => "Cluster size
89     $i", "data" => $lineChart,];
90         }
91
92         $boxPlot = [
93             "title" => "Box Plot", "data" => [
```

```
91         ["x" => 1, "min" => 2, "median" => 5, "
max" => 10, "q1" => 3, "q3" => 7,],
92         ["x" => 2, "min" => 1, "median" => 4, "
max" => 9, "q1" => 3, "q3" => 6,],
93         ["x" => 3, "min" => 1, "median" => 6, "
max" => 12, "q1" => 4, "q3" => 10,],
94     ],
95 ];
96
97     return [
98         'clusterCharts' => $clusterCharts,
99         'boxPlot'      => $boxPlot,
100    ];
101 }
102
103 public function getGridResult($type)
104 {
105     if (!in_array($type, $this->gridResult)) {
106         return [];
107     }
108
109     $data = [
110         [
111             'ssn' => '312-876-924',
112             'bno' => 'D1810',
113             'atc' => 'A02BC01',
114             'oen0' => '3501B',
115             'mi1' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
116             'mi2' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
117             'mi3' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
118             'death' => 'yes',
119         ],
120         [
121             'ssn' => '312-876-924',
122             'bno' => 'D1810',
123             'atc' => 'A02BC01',
124             'oen0' => '3501B',
125             'mi1' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
126             'mi2' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
127             'mi3' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
128             'death' => 'yes',
129         ],
130         [
131             'ssn' => '312-876-925',
132             'bno' => 'D1810',
133             'atc' => 'A02BC01',
134             'oen0' => '3501B',
```

File - /project/app/Repositories/SamiConfigRepository.php

```
135         'mi1' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
136         'mi2' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
137         'mi3' => '2001.12.-2005.01.',
138         'death' => 'no',
139     ],
140 ];
141
142     return $data;
143 }
144 }
145
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\AggregatedData;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Exceptions\
  InvalidFilteringException;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Exceptions\
  InvalidOrderingException;
8 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
9 use Illuminate\Support\Facades\DB;
10
11 class AggregatedDataRepository extends BaseRepository
12 {
13     public const EXTENDED_TYPE_REPOSITORIES = [
14         'disease_outpatient_icd' => BnoDataRepository::
15 class,
16         'disease_hospitalization_icd' => BnoDataRepository
17 ::class,
18         'health_intervention_outpatient_icpm' =>
19 OenoDataRepository::class,
20         'health_intervention_hospitalization_icmp' =>
21 OenoDataRepository::class,
22         'health_intervention_surgery_icpm' =>
23 OenoDataRepository::class,
24         'therapy_atc_code' => AtcDataRepository::class,
25     ];
26
27     protected $allowedOrders = [
28         'machine_name',
29         'value',
30         'count',
31     ];
32
33     protected $allowedFilters = [
34         'project_id',
35         'year',
36         'machine_name',
37         'machine_names',
38         'value',
39     ];
40
41     public function getModelClass()
42     {
43         return AggregatedData::class;
44     }
45 }
```

```
40
41     public function deleteByProjectId($projectId)
42     {
43         $items = $this->model->where(['project_id' =>
44 $projectId,])->get();
45         foreach ($items as $item) {
46             $item->delete();
47         }
48     }
49     public function deleteByFileId($fileId)
50     {
51         $items = $this->model->where(['file_id' => $fileId
52 ,])->get();
53         foreach ($items as $item) {
54             $item->delete();
55         }
56     }
57     public function deleteByProjectIdAndFileId($projectId
58 , $fileId)
59     {
60         $items = $this->model->where(['project_id' =>
61 $projectId, 'file_id' => $fileId,])->get();
62         foreach ($items as $item) {
63             $item->delete();
64         }
65     }
66     /**
67      * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD.ElseExpression)
68      * @SuppressWarnings(PHPMD.BooleanArgumentFlag)
69      */
70     public function increaseCount(array $attributes = [],
71 int $increase = 1, bool $aggregatedValue = false)
72     {
73         $status = false;
74         DB::transaction(function () use ($attributes,
75 $increase, $aggregatedValue, &$status) {
76             if (!$this->model->where($attributes)->exists
77 ()) {
78                 $this->store($attributes + ['count' =>
79 $increase, 'aggregated_value' => $aggregatedValue,]);
80             } else {
81                 $item = $this->model->where($attributes)->
82 first();
```

```
78         $item->count += $increase;
79         $item->save();
80     }
81
82     $status = true;
83     }, 5);
84
85     return $status;
86 }
87
88 private function getFiltered($filterInfo, $query)
89 {
90     if (!is_array($filterInfo) || empty($filterInfo
91 )) {
92         throw new InvalidFilteringException('No
93 filter info provided');
94     }
95     foreach ($filterInfo as $filterName =>
96 $filterValue) {
97         if (is_null($filterValue)) {
98             continue;
99         }
100         if (!in_array($filterName, $this->
101 getAllowedFilters())) {
102             throw new InvalidFilteringException('
103 Filter not allowed');
104         }
105         $query = $this->filterQuery($filterName,
106 $filterValue, $query);
107     }
108     return $query;
109 }
110
111 public function getFilteredOrderedWithLimit(
112 $filterInfo, $orderInfo, $limit)
113 {
114     $level = $filterInfo['level'];
115     unset($filterInfo['level']);
116
117     $category = $filterInfo['category'];
118     unset($filterInfo['category']);
119
120     $sub = $this->getFilteredOrderedSub($filterInfo,
121 $level, $category);
```

```
117
118     $query = DB::table(DB::raw("({$sub->toSql()}) as
sub"))
119         ->mergeBindings($sub->getQuery());
120
121     if (!is_null($orderInfo['order_by'])) {
122         if (is_null($orderInfo['sort_order'])) {
123             $orderInfo['sort_order'] = 'asc';
124         }
125
126         if (!in_array($orderInfo['order_by'], $this->
allowedOrders)
127             || !in_array($orderInfo['sort_order'], ['
asc', 'desc'])) {
128             throw new InvalidOrderingException();
129         }
130
131         $query = $query->orderBy($orderInfo['order_by
'], $orderInfo['sort_order']);
132     }
133
134     if (!is_null($limit)) {
135         $query->limit($limit);
136     }
137
138     return $query->get();
139 }
140
141 private function getFilteredOrderedSub($filterInfo,
$level, $category)
142 {
143     $machineNames = $this->collectMachineNames(
$category);
144     if (count($machineNames)) {
145         $filterInfo['machine_names'] = $machineNames;
146     }
147
148     $query = $this->model->newQuery();
149     if (!is_null($filterInfo)) {
150         $query = $this->getFiltered($filterInfo,
$query);
151     }
152
153     if (!empty($level)) {
154         $query->groupBy(['project_id', 'machine_name',
'value']);
155         $query->whereRaw('LENGTH(`value`) = ' .
```

```
155 $level);
156         return $query->select([DB::raw('SUM(count) AS
count'), 'project_id', 'year', 'machine_name', 'value']);
157     }
158
159     // we need all data, so we need to sum it...
160     if (empty($filterInfo['year'])) {
161         $query->groupBy(['project_id', 'machine_name',
'value']);
162         $query->where('aggregated_value', '!=', 1);
163         return $query->select([DB::raw('SUM(count) AS
count'), 'project_id', 'year', 'machine_name', 'value']);
164     }
165
166     $query->groupBy(['project_id', 'year', '
machine_name', 'value']);
167     $query->where('aggregated_value', '!=', 1);
168     return $query->select([DB::raw('SUM(count) AS
count'), 'project_id', 'year', 'machine_name', 'value']);
169 }
170
171 protected function filterQuery($filterName,
$filterValue, $query)
172 {
173     switch ($filterName) {
174         case 'project_id':
175         case 'year':
176         case 'machine_name':
177             return $query->where($filterName,
$filterValue);
178         case 'machine_names':
179             return $query->whereIn('machine_name',
$filterValue);
180         case 'value':
181             return $query->where($filterName, 'LIKE'
, $filterValue.'%');
182         default:
183             return $query;
184     }
185 }
186
187 /**
188  * @param $category
189  * @return array
190  */
191 private function collectMachineNames($category):
array
```

```
192     {
193         $machineNames = [];
194
195         switch ($category) {
196             case SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORY_ICD:
197                 $machineNames =
ColumnDefinitionRepository::ICD_MACHINE_NAMES;
198                 break;
199             case SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORY_ICPM:
200                 $machineNames =
ColumnDefinitionRepository::ICPM_MACHINE_NAMES;
201                 break;
202             case SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORY_ATC:
203                 $machineNames =
ColumnDefinitionRepository::ATC_MACHINE_NAMES;
204                 break;
205             case SamiConfigRepository::CATEGORY_DEATH:
206                 $machineNames =
ColumnDefinitionRepository::DEATH_MACHINE_NAMES;
207                 break;
208             default:
209                 if (!empty($category)) {
210                     $machineNames = [$category];
211                 }
212         }
213         return $machineNames;
214     }
215 }
216
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\ColumnCategory;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
7
8 class ColumnCategoryRepository extends BaseRepository
9 {
10     protected $allowedFilters = [
11         'parent_id',
12         'lft',
13         'rgt',
14         'depth',
15         'name',
16         'machine_name',
17     ];
18     protected $allowedOrders = [
19         'id',
20         'created_at',
21         'updated_at',
22         'parent_id',
23         'lft',
24         'rgt',
25         'depth',
26         'name',
27         'machine_name',
28     ];
29
30     public const ROOT_NAME = 'root';
31
32     public const RELATION_EQUALS = '=';
33     public const RELATION_NOT_EQUALS = '!=';
34     public const RELATION_GREATER_THAN = '>';
35     public const RELATION_GREATER_EQUALS = '>=';
36     public const RELATION_LESS_THAN = '<';
37     public const RELATION_LESS_EQUALS = '<=';
38
39     protected function filterQuery($filterName,
  $filterValue, $query)
40     {
41         switch ($filterName) {
42             case 'parent_id':
43                 return $query->where('parent_id',
  $filterValue);
44             case 'lft':
```

```
45         return $query->where('lft', $filterValue);
46     case 'rgt':
47         return $query->where('rgt', $filterValue);
48     case 'depth':
49         return $query->where('depth', $filterValue
50 );
51     case 'name':
52         return $query->where('name', 'LIKE', '%'
53 . $filterValue . '%');
54     case 'machine_name':
55         return $query->where('machine_name', 'LIKE
56 ', '%' . $filterValue . '%');
57     default:
58         return $query;
59     }
60 }
61
62 public static function getAllRelations()
63 {
64     return [
65         self::RELATION_EQUALS,
66         self::RELATION_NOT_EQUALS,
67         self::RELATION_GREATER_THAN,
68         self::RELATION_GREATER_EQUALS,
69         self::RELATION_LESS_THAN,
70         self::RELATION_LESS_EQUALS,
71     ];
72 }
73
74 public static function getStringRelations()
75 {
76     return [
77         self::RELATION_EQUALS,
78         self::RELATION_NOT_EQUALS,
79     ];
80 }
81
82 public function getRoot($parentMachineName)
83 {
84     return $this->model->where('machine_name',
85 $parentMachineName)
86     ->first();
87 }
88
89 public function getByMachineNameOrFail($machineName)
90 {
91     return $this->model->where('machine_name',
```

File - /project/app/Repositories/ColumnCategoryRepository.php

```
87 $machineName)->firstOrFail();
88     }
89
90     public function getModelClass()
91     {
92         return ColumnCategory::class;
93     }
94 }
95
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\ColumnDefinition;
6 use App\Models\File;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
8
9 class ColumnDefinitionRepository extends BaseRepository
10 {
11     protected $allowedFilters = [
12         'column_number',
13         'column_name',
14         'category',
15         'project_id',
16         'file_id',
17     ];
18     protected $allowedOrders = [
19         'id',
20         'created_at',
21         'updated_at',
22         'column_number',
23         'column_name',
24         'category',
25         'project_id',
26         'file_id',
27     ];
28     public const IDENTIFIER_MACHINE_NAMES = [
29         'identifier_patient_id',
30         'identifier_medical_record',
31         'identifier_medical_case',
32         'identifier_miscellaneous',
33     ];
34     public const ICD_MACHINE_NAMES = [
35         'disease_outpatient_icd',
36         'disease_hospitalization_icd',
37     ];
38     public const ATC_MACHINE_NAMES = [
39         'therapy_atc_code',
40     ];
41     public const ICPM_MACHINE_NAMES = [
42         'health_intervention_outpatient_icpm',
43         'health_intervention_surgery_icpm',
44     ];
45     public const DATE_MACHINE_NAMES = [
46         'timestamp_date',
```

```
47     ];
48     public const DEATH_MACHINE_NAMES = [
49         'patient_decease_clinical_diagnosis',
50         'patient_decease_post_mortem_diagnosis',
51     ];
52
53     public function getIdentifierColumnMachineNameByFile(
54     File $file)
55     {
56         /** @var ColumnDefinition $columnDefinition */
57         $columnDefinition = $this->model->newQuery()
58             ->where('file_id', $file->id)
59             ->whereIn('category', static::
60     IDENTIFIER_MACHINE_NAMES)
61             ->first();
62         return $columnDefinition->category ?? null;
63     }
64
65     public function getOrderedListByFileId($fileId)
66     {
67         return $this->model->newQuery()
68             ->where('file_id', $fileId)
69             ->orderBy('column_number', 'asc')
70             ->get();
71     }
72
73     protected function filterQuery($filterName,
74     $filterValue, $query)
75     {
76         switch ($filterName) {
77             case 'column_number':
78                 return $query->where('column_number',
79     $filterValue);
80             case 'column_name':
81                 return $query->where('column_name', 'LIKE'
82     , '%' . $filterValue . '%');
83             case 'category':
84                 return $query->where('category',
85     $filterValue);
86             case 'project_id':
87                 return $query->where('project_id',
88     $filterValue);
89             case 'file_id':
90                 return $query->where('file_id',
91     $filterValue);
92             default:
93                 return $query;
94         }
95     }
```

File - /project/app/Repositories/ColumnDefinitionRepository.php

```
86     }
87     public function getModelClass()
88     {
89         return ColumnDefinition::class;
90     }
91 }
92
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories;
4
5 use App\Models\SamiConfigMilestone;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Repositories\
  BaseRepository;
7
8 class SamiConfigMilestoneRepository extends BaseRepository
9 {
10     protected $allowedFilters = [
11         'sami_config_id',
12     ];
13
14     protected $allowedOrders = [
15         'id',
16         'sami_config_id',
17         'created_at',
18         'updated_at',
19     ];
20
21     protected function filterQuery($filterName,
22     $filterValue, $query)
23     {
24         switch ($filterName) {
25             case 'sami_config_id':
26                 return $query->where('sami_config_id',
27     $filterValue);
28             default:
29                 return $query;
30         }
31     }
32
33     public function getModelClass()
34     {
35         return SamiConfigMilestone::class;
36     }
37 }
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Repositories\Traits;
4
5 trait GetByCode
6 {
7     public function getByCode($code, $projectId)
8     {
9         return $this->model
10             ->where('code', $code)
11             ->where('project_id', $projectId)
12             ->first();
13     }
14 }
15
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\Models\File;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
8
9 class FileTransformer extends BaseResourceTransformer
  implements ResourceTransformerInterface
10 {
11
12     public static function getResourceKey()
13     {
14         return 'file';
15     }
16
17     public function transform(File $file)
18     {
19         return [
20             'id' => (int) $file->id,
21             'user_id' => (int) $file->user_id,
22             'project_id' => (int) $file->project_id,
23             'file_name' => (string) $file->file_name,
24             'size' => (int) $file->size,
25             'preview' => (array) $file->preview,
26         ];
27     }
28 }
29
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\User;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
8
9 class UserTransformer extends BaseResourceTransformer
  implements ResourceTransformerInterface
10 {
11     public static function getResourceKey()
12     {
13         return 'user';
14     }
15
16     public function transform(User $user)
17     {
18         return [
19             'id' => $user->id,
20             'created_at' => $user->created_at->
  toDateTimeString(),
21             'updated_at' => $user->updated_at->
  toDateTimeString(),
22             'name' => $user->name,
23             'email' => $user->email,
24         ];
25     }
26 }
27
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\Models\Project;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
8
9 class ProjectTransformer extends BaseResourceTransformer
  implements ResourceTransformerInterface
10 {
11     public static function getResourceKey()
12     {
13         return 'project';
14     }
15
16     public function transform(Project $project)
17     {
18         return [
19             'id' => $project->id,
20             'created_at' => $project->created_at->
  toDateTimeString(),
21             'updated_at' => $project->updated_at->
  toDateTimeString(),
22             'name' => $project->name,
23             'archived' => $project->archived,
24             'upload_done' => $project->upload_done,
25         ];
26     }
27 }
28
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\Models\SamiConfig;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\Fractal;
8 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
9 use League\Fractal\Serializer\JsonApiSerializer;
10 use App\Repositories\SamiConfigRepository;
11
12 class SamiConfigTransformer extends
  BaseResourceTransformer implements
  ResourceTransformerInterface
13 {
14     public static function getResourceKey()
15     {
16         return 'sami_config';
17     }
18
19     public function transform(SamiConfig $samiConfig)
20     {
21         $samiConfigMilestoneTransformer = new
  SamiConfigMilestoneTransformer();
22         $samiConfigMilestoneFractal = new Fractal(new
  JsonApiSerializer());
23         $milestones = $samiConfigMilestoneFractal->
  collection(
24             $samiConfig->samiConfigMilestone()->get(),
25             $samiConfigMilestoneTransformer,
26             $samiConfigMilestoneTransformer::
  getResourceKey()
27         );
28
29         $samiConfigRepository = new SamiConfigRepository
  ();
30
31         return [
32             'id' => $samiConfig->id,
33             'project_id' => $samiConfig->project_id,
34             'factors' => $samiConfig->factors,
35             'type' => $samiConfig->type,
36             'name' => $samiConfig->name,
37             'starting_date' => $samiConfig->starting_date,
38             'ending_date' => $samiConfig->ending_date,
```

```
39         'category' => $samiConfig->category,  
40         'code' => $samiConfig->code,  
41         'relative_range_start' => $samiConfig->  
relative_range_start,  
42         'relative_range_end' => $samiConfig->  
relative_range_end,  
43         'created_at' => $samiConfig->created_at->  
toDateTimeString(),  
44         'updated_at' => $samiConfig->updated_at->  
toDateTimeString(),  
45         'milestones' => $milestones,  
46         'chartResult' => $samiConfigRepository->  
getChartResult($samiConfig->type),  
47         'gridResult' => $samiConfigRepository->  
getGridResult($samiConfig->type),  
48     ];  
49     }  
50 }  
51
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\Models\AggregatedData;
6 use App\Repositories\AggregatedDataRepository;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
8 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
9
10 class AggregatedDataTransformer extends
  BaseResourceTransformer implements
  ResourceTransformerInterface
11 {
12     public static function getResourceKey()
13     {
14         return 'aggregatedData';
15     }
16
17     public function transform($aggregatedData)
18     {
19         return [
20             'id' => null,
21             'project_id' => (int) $aggregatedData->
  project_id,
22             'machine_name' => (string) $aggregatedData->
  machine_name,
23             'value' => (string) $aggregatedData->value,
24             'count' => (int) $aggregatedData->count,
25             'meta' => [
26                 'extended_value' => $this->
  getExtendedValue($aggregatedData),
27             ],
28         ];
29     }
30
31     private function getExtendedValue($aggregatedData)
32     {
33         if (array_key_exists(
34             $aggregatedData->machine_name,
35             AggregatedDataRepository::
  EXTENDED_TYPE_REPOSITORIES
36         )) {
37             $repositotyClass =
38                 AggregatedDataRepository::
  EXTENDED_TYPE_REPOSITORIES[$aggregatedData->machine_name];
```

File - /project/app/Transformers/Api/AggregatedDataTransformer.php

```
39         $repositoty = new $repositotyClass();
40         $extendedData = $repositoty->getByCode(
$aggregatedData->value, $aggregatedData->project_id);
41         if ($extendedData) {
42             return $aggregatedData->value . ' - ' .
$extendedData->name;
43         }
44     }
45     return $aggregatedData->value;
46 }
47 }
48
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\Models\ColumnCategory;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
8
9 class ColumnCategoryTransformer extends
  BaseResourceTransformer implements
  ResourceTransformerInterface
10 {
11     public static function getResourceKey()
12     {
13         return 'column_category';
14     }
15
16     public function transform(ColumnCategory
  $columnCategory)
17     {
18         return [
19             'id' => $columnCategory->id,
20             'created_at' => $columnCategory->created_at->
  toDateTimeString(),
21             'updated_at' => $columnCategory->updated_at->
  toDateTimeString(),
22             'parent_id' => $columnCategory->parent_id,
23             'lft' => $columnCategory->lft,
24             'rgt' => $columnCategory->rgt,
25             'depth' => $columnCategory->depth,
26             'name' => $columnCategory->name,
27             'machine_name' => $columnCategory->
  machine_name,
28             'logical_conditions' => $columnCategory->
  logical_conditions,
29         ];
30     }
31 }
32
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\Models\ColumnDefinition;
6 use App\Repositories\ColumnCategoryRepository;
7 use App\Repositories\ColumnDefinitionRepository;
8 use App\Repositories\FileRepository;
9 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
10 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\Fractal;
11 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
12 use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\ModelNotFoundException;
13 use Illuminate\Support\Arr;
14 use League\Fractal\Serializer\JsonApiSerializer;
15
16 class ColumnDefinitionTransformer extends
  BaseResourceTransformer implements
  ResourceTransformerInterface
17 {
18     public static function getResourceKey()
19     {
20         return 'column_definition';
21     }
22
23     public function transform(ColumnDefinition
  $columnDefinition)
24     {
25         $fileType = $columnDefinition->file->type ?? null;
26         $category = $this->rewriteCategory($fileType,
  $columnDefinition->category);
27         return [
28             'id' => $columnDefinition->id,
29             'created_at' => $columnDefinition->created_at
  ->toDateTimeString(),
30             'updated_at' => $columnDefinition->updated_at
  ->toDateTimeString(),
31             'column_number' => $columnDefinition->
  column_number,
32             'column_name' => $columnDefinition->
  column_name,
33             'category' => $category,
34             'project_id' => $columnDefinition->project_id,
35             'file_id' => $columnDefinition->file_id,
36             'meta' => [
37                 'column_category' => $this->
```

```

37 getColumnCategoryOutput($columnDefinition),
38     ],
39 ];
40 }
41 private function rewriteCategory($fileType, $category)
42 {
43     if ($fileType !== FileRepository::PRIMARY_TYPE &&
44         in_array($fileType, FileRepository::DATA_TYPES
45     ) {
46         if (in_array($category,
47             ColumnDefinitionRepository::IDENTIFIER_MACHINE_NAMES)) {
48             $category = 'id';
49         }
50         if (in_array($category,
51             ColumnDefinitionRepository::DATE_MACHINE_NAMES)) {
52             $category = 'date';
53         }
54         if (in_array(
55             $category,
56             array_merge(
57                 ColumnDefinitionRepository::
58                 ICD_MACHINE_NAMES,
59                 ColumnDefinitionRepository::
60                 ICPM_MACHINE_NAMES,
61                 ColumnDefinitionRepository::
62                 ATC_MACHINE_NAMES
63             )
64         )) {
65             $category = 'code';
66         }
67     }
68     return $category;
69 }
70 private function getColumnCategoryOutput(
71     ColumnDefinition $columnDefinition)
72 {
73     $fractal = new Fractal(new JsonSerializer());
74     $categoryRepository = new ColumnCategoryRepository
75     ();
76     try {
77         $category = $categoryRepository->
78         getByNameOrFail($columnDefinition->category);
79         return $fractal->item(
80             $category,
81             new ColumnCategoryTransformer(),
82             ColumnCategoryTransformer::getResourceKey

```

File - /project/app/Transformers/Api/ColumnDefinitionTransformer.php

```
74 ()
75     );
76     } catch (ModelNotFoundException $exception) {
77         return null;
78     }
79 }
80 }
81
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\Models\SamiConfigMilestone;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
8
9 class SamiConfigMilestoneTransformer extends
  BaseResourceTransformer implements
  ResourceTransformerInterface
10 {
11     public static function getResourceKey()
12     {
13         return 'sami_config_milestone';
14     }
15
16     public function transform(SamiConfigMilestone
  $samiConfigMilestone)
17     {
18         return [
19             'id' => $samiConfigMilestone->id,
20             'sami_config_id' => $samiConfigMilestone->
  sami_config_id,
21             'milestone_category' => $samiConfigMilestone->
  milestone_category,
22             'milestone_code' => $samiConfigMilestone->
  milestone_code,
23             'milestone_relative_range_start' =>
  $samiConfigMilestone->milestone_relative_range_start,
24             'milestone_relative_range_end' =>
  $samiConfigMilestone->milestone_relative_range_end,
25             'milestone_frequency' => $samiConfigMilestone
  ->milestone_frequency,
26             'created_at' => $samiConfigMilestone->
  created_at->toDateTimeString(),
27             'updated_at' => $samiConfigMilestone->
  updated_at->toDateTimeString(),
28         ];
29     }
30 }
31
```

```
1 <?php
2
3 namespace App\Transformers\Api;
4
5 use App\Models\ColumnCategory;
6 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  BaseResourceTransformer;
7 use Cheppers\LaravelApiGenerator\Transformers\
  ResourceTransformerInterface;
8
9 class ColumnCategoryHierarchyTransformer extends
  BaseResourceTransformer implements
  ResourceTransformerInterface
10 {
11     public static function getResourceKey()
12     {
13         return 'column_category';
14     }
15
16     public function transform(ColumnCategory
  $columnCategory)
17     {
18         return $this->getChildren($columnCategory);
19     }
20
21     public function getChildren(ColumnCategory
  $columnCategory)
22     {
23         $transformed = [];
24         foreach ($columnCategory->children as $child) {
25             $transformed[] = [
26                 'name' => $child->name,
27                 'machine_name' => $child->machine_name,
28                 'items' => $this->getChildren($child),
29             ];
30         }
31         return $transformed;
32     }
33 }
34
```